

Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Orders 14

The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16991>

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Abstract

*This work summarizes author's previous works on magic squares of order 14. It brings different types of magic square such as **block-wise, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered, cornered, designs, styles, etc.** In terms of aspects, we have considered the idea of **Pythagorean triples, upside-down, mirror-looking, water reflection, perfect square sum entries, Latin square distributions, Algebraic magic squares, etc.***

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1 Introduction

In the previous works [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25], the author worked with **block-wise** constructions of magic squares. The work is from the orders 8 to 45. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. These possibilities are based on divisions of magic squares. The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we shall bring **blocks** for the **block-wise** magic squares. That is, whenever is possible, we shall try to bring blocks of equal sum magic squares. In some cases, they are **magic, semi-magic, pandiagonal**, etc. When the question come to **bimagic** squares, in some cases, we have **semi-bimagic** squares.

On the other hand the idea of **bordered** magic squares is well explained in the work by H.White [4, 5]. Few results in this direction can be seen in author's work [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. In some case, the magic rectangles are also used to write it in different styles. Most of the author's work on magic squares in on different types, and is summarized below in details according to topics:

1. *Digital Fonts: Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
2. *Two Digits Universal Magic Squares.*
3. *Different Digits Magic Squares.*
4. *Pythagorean Triples Magic Squares.*
5. *Block-Wise Magic Squares.*
6. *Selfie and Palindromic Type Magic Squares.*
7. *Block Bordered Magic Squares.*
8. *Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares.*
9. *Magic Crosses, Letters and Numbers.*
10. *Cornered Magic Squares.*
11. *Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
12. *Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
13. *Multiple-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
14. *Striped Magic Squares.*
15. *Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*

16. *Water reflection Magic Squares.*

17. *Algebraic Magic Squares.*

The aim of this work is to write magic squares of order 16 in different ways and styles using the aspects of **blocks**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **magic rectangles**, **corner-type**, **single-digit**, **double-digit**, etc.

More details on these works on **magic squares** can be seen in author's web-sites:

(i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>

(ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>

2 Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 14

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 14 is given by

$$S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14 \times (1 + 14^2)}{2} = 1379.$$

Since order 14 is double of prime number, it doesn't give us block-wise construction of magic square of order 14. Below are few examples of different ways of writing magic squares of order 14.

2.1 General Magic Squares

Example 2.1.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													1379
1	95	191	112	138	78	58	32	17	159	146	178	125	49	1379
147	16	110	176	188	127	87	117	4	53	70	83	38	163	1379
126	162	31	137	172	63	80	6	47	26	97	99	149	184	1379
190	111	150	46	155	115	5	77	34	170	23	96	140	67	1379
164	84	55	12	121	86	29	101	133	62	173	25	186	148	1379
104	10	89	37	21	166	179	154	195	74	44	134	59	113	1379
19	35	132	57	3	153	196	165	180	92	122	51	72	102	1379
45	65	71	90	36	193	152	181	168	119	130	2	103	24	1379
30	43	60	73	94	182	167	194	151	107	7	118	22	131	1379
68	144	156	27	75	48	105	93	120	136	183	42	11	171	1379
81	187	175	114	69	18	135	52	85	14	106	143	160	40	1379
139	174	8	161	142	108	116	15	79	185	39	61	54	98	1379
177	129	123	192	56	33	20	64	100	141	82	158	91	13	1379
88	124	28	145	109	9	50	128	66	41	157	189	169	76	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is constructed based on a pair of self-orthogonalized latin squares.

For more details refer author's work [22, 23, 24]

2.2 Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.2.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													1379
183	172	174	176	192	194	26	24	22	20	6	4	2	184	1379
19	159	150	152	167	169	48	46	44	31	29	27	160	178	1379
17	43	139	132	134	146	66	64	62	52	50	140	154	180	1379
15	40	61	123	118	129	80	78	69	67	124	136	157	182	1379
11	39	59	76	111	108	90	88	82	112	121	138	158	186	1379
9	34	55	75	87	97	102	91	104	110	122	142	163	188	1379
1	32	49	70	81	92	103	98	101	116	127	148	165	196	1379
179	155	137	120	113	106	93	100	95	84	77	60	42	18	1379
181	156	141	125	114	99	96	105	94	83	72	56	41	16	1379
185	161	143	126	85	89	107	109	115	86	71	54	36	12	1379
187	162	144	73	79	68	117	119	128	130	74	53	35	10	1379
189	164	57	65	63	51	131	133	135	145	147	58	33	8	1379
190	37	47	45	30	28	149	151	153	166	168	170	38	7	1379
13	25	23	21	5	3	171	173	175	177	191	193	195	14	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is well-known *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 14, where removing the upper borderes, still are left with magic squares of orders 13,12,11, etc.

Example 2.3.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184	1379
195	124	27	77	98	48	145	104	54	151	166	69	119	2	1379
3	29	76	123	144	97	50	150	103	56	71	118	165	194	1379
193	75	125	28	49	146	96	55	152	102	117	167	70	4	1379
5	157	60	110	113	63	160	83	33	130	139	42	92	192	1379
191	62	109	156	159	112	65	129	82	35	44	91	138	6	1379
177	108	158	61	64	161	111	34	131	81	90	140	43	20	1379
171	93	143	46	31	128	78	73	170	120	99	149	52	26	1379
25	47	94	141	126	79	32	168	121	74	53	100	147	172	1379
173	142	45	95	80	30	127	122	72	169	148	51	101	24	1379
23	114	164	67	58	155	105	40	137	87	84	134	37	174	1379
175	68	115	162	153	106	59	135	88	41	38	85	132	22	1379
21	163	66	116	107	57	154	89	39	136	133	36	86	176	1379
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

*It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 14 embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 12. It is composed of equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3.*

Example 2.4.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184	1379
195	81	134	27	152	82	133	28	151	83	132	29	150	2	1379
3	44	135	98	117	43	136	97	118	42	137	96	119	194	1379
193	170	45	116	63	169	46	115	64	168	47	114	65	4	1379
5	99	80	153	62	100	79	154	61	101	78	155	60	192	1379
191	84	131	30	149	85	130	31	148	86	129	32	147	6	1379
177	41	138	95	120	40	139	94	121	39	140	93	122	20	1379
171	167	48	113	66	166	49	112	67	165	50	111	68	26	1379
25	102	77	156	59	103	76	157	58	104	75	158	57	172	1379
173	87	128	33	146	88	127	34	145	89	126	35	144	24	1379
23	38	141	92	123	37	142	91	124	36	143	90	125	174	1379
175	164	51	110	69	163	52	109	70	162	53	108	71	22	1379
21	105	74	159	56	106	73	160	55	107	72	161	54	176	1379
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

*It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 14 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is composed 9 equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4.*

Example 2.5.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184	1379
195	27	163	162	155	34	50	28	164	161	156	33	49	2	1379
3	146	58	138	59	67	123	145	57	137	60	68	124	194	1379
193	122	115	83	90	106	75	121	116	84	89	105	76	4	1379
5	98	82	107	114	91	99	97	81	108	113	92	100	192	1379
191	51	130	66	131	139	74	52	129	65	132	140	73	6	1379
177	147	43	35	42	154	170	148	44	36	41	153	169	20	1379
171	29	165	160	157	32	48	30	166	159	158	31	47	26	1379
25	144	56	136	61	69	125	143	55	135	62	70	126	172	1379
173	120	117	85	88	104	77	119	118	86	87	103	78	24	1379
23	96	80	109	112	93	101	95	79	110	111	94	102	174	1379
175	53	128	64	133	141	72	54	127	63	134	142	71	22	1379
21	149	45	37	40	152	168	150	46	38	39	151	167	176	1379
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

*It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 14 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is composed 4 equal sums magic squares of order 6.*

Example 2.6.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/						https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/						©IJT	1379
14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184	1379
195	166	164	29	170	30	32	148	146	47	152	48	50	2	1379
3	28	43	156	37	158	169	46	61	138	55	140	151	194	1379
193	34	38	157	44	155	163	52	56	139	62	137	145	4	1379
5	36	160	39	154	41	161	54	142	57	136	59	143	192	1379
191	162	153	42	159	40	35	144	135	60	141	58	53	6	1379
177	165	33	168	27	167	31	147	51	150	45	149	49	20	1379
171	112	110	83	116	84	86	130	128	65	134	66	68	26	1379
25	82	97	102	91	104	115	64	79	120	73	122	133	172	1379
173	88	92	103	98	101	109	70	74	121	80	119	127	24	1379
23	90	106	93	100	95	107	72	124	75	118	77	125	174	1379
175	108	99	96	105	94	89	126	117	78	123	76	71	22	1379
21	111	87	114	81	113	85	129	69	132	63	131	67	176	1379
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 14 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is composed 4 equal sums single-digit bordered magic squares of order 6.

For more details refer author's work [22, 23, 24]

2.3 Cornered Magic Squares

Example 2.7.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
97	102	91	104	83	114	77	120	132	65	169	28	192	5	1379
92	103	98	101	111	86	117	80	66	131	149	48	183	14	1379
106	93	100	95	115	82	130	67	60	137	159	38	13	184	1379
99	96	105	94	88	109	123	74	134	63	45	152	171	26	1379
113	81	112	108	87	90	72	125	51	146	158	39	178	19	1379
84	116	85	89	107	110	69	128	139	58	150	47	11	186	1379
79	70	68	126	122	78	124	121	61	136	164	33	7	190	1379
118	127	129	71	75	119	76	73	144	53	40	157	23	174	1379
49	64	50	62	145	54	140	138	142	141	42	155	25	172	1379
148	133	147	135	52	143	57	59	56	55	31	166	17	180	1379
46	27	35	168	167	153	163	41	160	36	32	154	189	8	1379
151	170	162	29	30	44	34	156	37	161	43	165	182	15	1379
194	187	16	1	177	195	6	21	24	12	4	175	179	188	1379
3	10	181	196	20	2	191	176	173	185	193	22	9	18	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is a cornered magic square of order 14.

For more details refer author's work [35, 36, 37, 38].

2.4 Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.8.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
153	31	168	177	19	33	169	160	22	196	48	7	186	10	1379
166	44	29	20	178	164	28	37	175	1	149	190	187	11	1379
183	14	139	134	69	144	56	78	65	126	124	50	43	154	1379
185	12	63	58	128	53	141	119	132	71	147	73	17	180	1379
23	174	57	140	89	102	106	83	96	115	75	122	41	156	1379
36	161	68	129	116	95	109	98	88	85	80	117	171	26	1379
165	32	54	143	114	113	82	101	91	90	59	138	179	18	1379
172	25	60	137	81	84	108	110	97	111	125	72	34	163	1379
4	193	135	62	105	93	94	100	112	87	49	148	21	176	1379
27	170	146	51	86	104	92	99	107	103	120	77	35	162	1379
13	184	133	67	121	145	123	55	79	131	70	61	188	9	1379
167	30	130	64	76	52	74	142	118	66	136	127	46	151	1379
40	152	189	191	42	182	150	2	38	24	16	3	192	158	1379
45	157	8	6	155	15	47	195	159	173	181	194	39	5	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is a double-digit bordered magic square of order based on four equal sums magic rectangles of each borders. Blocks of order 2×2 has no property. Removing the external borders still we left with magic squares of lower orders 10 and 6.

Example 2.9.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
185	169	196	192	3	10	34	6	193	16	36	30	157	152	1379
12	28	1	5	194	187	163	191	4	181	161	167	40	45	1379
18	179	147	61	75	52	58	130	65	128	123	146	151	46	1379
183	14	50	136	122	145	139	67	132	69	74	51	158	39	1379
155	42	118	79	81	115	114	113	82	86	77	120	15	182	1379
20	177	78	119	110	88	108	89	91	105	143	54	43	154	1379
38	159	76	121	104	103	95	96	100	93	117	80	160	37	1379
171	26	135	62	98	94	101	102	97	99	124	73	166	31	1379
184	13	131	66	87	106	90	107	109	92	60	137	41	156	1379
23	174	53	144	111	85	83	84	112	116	70	127	195	2	1379
172	25	72	49	133	129	71	59	134	140	56	142	48	149	1379
21	176	125	148	64	68	126	138	63	57	141	55	8	189	1379
175	180	7	150	178	33	44	32	162	29	9	24	170	186	1379
22	17	190	47	19	164	153	165	35	168	188	173	27	11	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

*It is a also **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 14 written in a different form. Here we don't have blocks of order 2×2 . Removing the external borders still we left with magic squares of lower orders 10 and 6.*

Example 2.10.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
39	158	73	124	81	115	114	113	82	86	139	58	180	17	1379
157	40	123	74	110	88	108	89	91	105	137	60	179	18	1379
156	41	75	122	104	103	95	96	100	93	136	61	19	178	1379
155	42	121	76	98	94	101	102	97	99	62	135	20	177	1379
43	154	120	77	87	106	90	107	109	92	134	63	21	176	1379
44	153	118	79	111	85	83	84	112	116	64	133	175	22	1379
45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

*It is a **double-digit cyclic bordered** magic square of order based on four equal sums magic rectangles of each borders. Since here we don't have blocks of order 2×2 we call these types of magic squares as cyclic. Removing the external borders still we left with magic squares of lower orders 10 and 6.*

For more details refer author's work [33, 34]

2.5 Striped Magic Squares

Example 2.11.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
185	169	196	192	3	10	34	6	193	16	36	30	157	152	1379
12	28	1	5	194	187	163	191	4	181	161	167	40	45	1379
18	179	147	61	75	52	58	130	65	128	123	146	151	46	1379
183	14	50	136	122	145	139	67	132	69	74	51	158	39	1379
155	42	118	79	90	107	83	114	109	88	77	120	15	182	1379
20	177	78	119	91	106	82	115	112	85	143	54	43	154	1379
38	159	76	121	105	92	113	84	86	111	117	80	160	37	1379
171	26	135	62	108	89	116	81	87	110	124	73	166	31	1379
184	13	131	66	101	95	100	93	103	99	60	137	41	156	1379
23	174	53	144	96	102	97	104	94	98	70	127	195	2	1379
172	25	72	49	133	129	71	59	134	140	56	142	48	149	1379
21	176	125	148	64	68	126	138	63	57	141	55	8	189	1379
175	180	7	150	178	33	44	32	162	29	9	24	170	186	1379
22	17	190	47	19	164	153	165	35	168	188	173	27	11	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

Example 2.12.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
39	158	73	124	90	107	83	114	109	88	139	58	180	17	1379
157	40	123	74	91	106	82	115	112	85	137	60	179	18	1379
156	41	75	122	105	92	113	84	86	111	136	61	19	178	1379
155	42	121	76	108	89	116	81	87	110	62	135	20	177	1379
43	154	120	77	101	95	100	93	103	99	134	63	21	176	1379
44	153	118	79	96	102	97	104	94	98	64	133	175	22	1379
45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

Example 2.13.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	1379				
113	116	82	83	79	118	128	69	149	48	170	27	19	178	1379
84	81	115	114	74	123	71	126	148	49	172	25	189	8	1379
117	124	75	78	120	77	133	64	144	53	40	157	12	185	1379
80	73	122	119	121	76	130	67	56	141	29	168	181	16	1379
62	65	127	134	131	72	68	129	46	151	33	164	4	193	1379
135	132	70	63	66	125	61	136	137	60	163	34	187	10	1379
139	45	147	142	54	59	150	52	51	146	153	44	13	184	1379
58	152	50	55	143	138	47	145	57	140	155	42	175	22	1379
28	35	161	166	41	26	160	158	43	167	32	165	176	21	1379
169	162	36	31	156	171	37	39	154	30	38	159	20	177	1379
182	192	186	23	1	6	24	183	3	7	180	195	18	179	1379
15	5	11	174	196	191	173	14	194	190	17	2	188	9	1379
85	111	100	109	89	107	106	92	104	94	95	101	87	99	1379
112	86	97	88	108	90	91	105	93	103	102	96	110	98	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

The magic squares given in Examples 2.11, 2.12 and 2.13 we call as **striped** magic squares. We call them as **striped** as these are based on the equal width of order 2. The only different is in the length of the each magic rectangles.

For more details refer author's work [39, 41, 45].

2.6 Different Styles of Magic Squares

Example 2.14.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													1379
7	185	188	2	8	193	10	6	194	192	25	176	166	27	1379
196	183	182	16	179	20	13	17	178	1	32	159	38	165	1379
186	14	15	181	18	177	184	180	19	11	29	37	160	168	1379
5	12	9	195	189	4	187	191	3	190	175	36	161	22	1379
67	136	126	65	112	110	83	116	84	86	169	163	34	28	1379
125	119	78	72	82	97	102	91	104	115	24	33	164	173	1379
128	80	117	69	88	92	103	98	101	109	167	162	35	30	1379
66	77	120	131	90	106	93	100	95	107	171	40	157	26	1379
68	118	79	129	108	99	96	105	94	89	23	158	39	174	1379
133	73	124	64	111	87	114	81	113	85	170	21	31	172	1379
62	122	75	135	150	52	49	151	149	44	147	155	43	45	1379
70	76	121	127	41	57	60	56	143	53	138	139	142	156	1379
134	123	74	63	51	140	137	141	54	144	59	58	55	146	1379
132	61	71	130	152	145	148	46	48	153	50	42	154	47	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is composed of **bordered** magic rectangles having **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 6 in the middle.

Example 2.15.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	1379				
7	192	1	194	35	164	36	157	160	39	15	184	9	186	1379
2	193	8	191	38	43	153	156	42	159	10	185	16	183	1379
196	3	190	5	163	154	44	41	155	34	188	11	182	13	1379
189	6	195	4	158	33	161	40	37	162	181	14	187	12	1379
71	74	127	122	81	115	114	113	82	86	47	50	151	146	1379
128	79	118	69	110	88	108	89	91	105	152	55	142	45	1379
72	117	80	125	104	103	95	96	100	93	48	141	56	149	1379
121	120	77	76	98	94	101	102	97	99	145	144	53	52	1379
124	78	119	73	87	106	90	107	109	92	148	54	143	49	1379
75	123	70	126	111	85	83	84	112	116	51	147	46	150	1379
31	168	25	170	59	140	60	133	136	63	23	176	17	178	1379
26	169	32	167	62	67	129	132	66	135	18	177	24	175	1379
172	27	166	29	139	130	68	65	131	58	180	19	174	21	1379
165	30	171	28	134	57	137	64	61	138	173	22	179	20	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is composed of bordered magic rectangles and magic squares.

Example 2.16.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
13	186	188	7	63	123	136	132	67	70	41	158	160	35	1379
6	169	28	191	135	82	111	81	120	62	34	50	147	163	1379
187	22	175	10	64	78	101	96	119	133	159	48	149	38	1379
185	172	25	12	59	75	100	97	122	138	161	144	53	36	1379
189	23	174	8	68	121	106	91	76	129	165	51	146	32	1379
182	26	171	15	137	113	92	105	84	60	154	54	143	43	1379
1	179	18	196	128	114	99	98	83	69	29	151	46	168	1379
3	173	24	194	72	87	107	90	110	125	31	145	52	166	1379
16	20	177	181	131	112	89	108	85	66	44	141	56	153	1379
5	178	19	192	57	118	93	104	79	140	33	45	152	164	1379
193	176	21	4	139	117	103	94	80	58	157	148	49	40	1379
195	17	180	2	73	88	95	102	109	124	167	55	142	30	1379
14	27	170	183	126	77	86	116	115	71	42	150	47	155	1379
190	11	9	184	127	74	61	65	130	134	162	39	37	156	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is composed of three bordered magic rectangles.

2.7 Embedded Magic Squares

Example 2.17.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
37	160	139	132	134	146	66	64	62	52	50	140	183	14	1379
159	38	61	74	68	128	130	117	79	119	73	136	181	16	1379
39	158	59	71	112	110	83	116	84	86	126	138	180	17	1379
157	40	55	72	82	97	102	91	104	115	125	142	179	18	1379
156	41	49	77	88	92	103	98	101	109	120	148	19	178	1379
155	42	137	127	90	106	93	100	95	107	70	60	20	177	1379
43	154	141	122	108	99	96	105	94	89	75	56	21	176	1379
44	153	143	121	111	87	114	81	113	85	76	54	175	22	1379
45	152	144	124	129	69	67	80	118	78	123	53	23	174	1379
47	150	57	65	63	51	131	133	135	145	147	58	173	24	1379
151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is *double-digit cyclic bordered magic square* of order 14 embedded with a *single-digit bordered magic square* of order 10.

Example 2.18.

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1379	
153	31	168	177	19	33	169	160	22	196	48	7	186	10	1379
166	44	29	20	178	164	28	37	175	1	149	190	187	11	1379
183	14	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	43	154	1379
185	12	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	17	180	1379
23	174	73	124	86	110	83	116	84	112	139	58	41	156	1379
36	161	123	74	115	97	102	91	104	82	137	60	171	26	1379
165	32	75	122	109	92	103	98	101	88	136	61	179	18	1379
172	25	121	76	107	106	93	100	95	90	62	135	34	163	1379
4	193	120	77	89	99	96	105	94	108	134	63	21	176	1379
27	170	118	79	85	87	114	81	113	111	64	133	35	162	1379
13	184	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	188	9	1379
167	30	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	46	151	1379
40	152	189	191	42	182	150	2	38	24	16	3	192	158	1379
45	157	8	6	155	15	47	195	159	173	181	194	39	5	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

It is double-digit bordered magic square of order 14 embedded with a double-digit cyclic bordered magic square of order 10. It again contains a single-digit bordered magic square of order 6.

For mor details refer author’s work [6, 7, 8, 10, 49]

3 Different Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 14

3.1 Latin Square Distributions

Let's consider the Latin square distributions of magic square of order 14 given in Example 3.2.

Example 3.1. *Let's consider a magic square of 14 with Latin square decomposition as given below:*

(A)														105
1	4	11	5	8	2	9	3	7	14	12	13	6	10	105
14	2	5	11	6	3	10	4	8	12	13	7	1	9	105
12	14	3	6	11	4	1	5	9	13	8	2	10	7	105
13	12	14	4	7	5	2	6	10	9	3	1	8	11	105
10	13	12	14	5	6	3	7	1	4	2	9	11	8	105
7	8	9	10	1	11	13	14	12	6	5	4	3	2	105
9	10	1	2	3	14	12	11	13	8	7	6	5	4	105
6	7	8	9	10	12	14	13	11	5	4	3	2	1	105
8	9	10	1	2	13	11	12	14	7	6	5	4	3	105
3	11	4	7	9	1	8	2	6	10	14	12	13	5	105
11	3	6	8	4	10	7	1	5	2	9	14	12	13	105
2	5	7	3	13	9	6	10	4	11	1	8	14	12	105
4	6	2	13	12	8	5	9	3	1	11	10	7	14	105
5	1	13	12	14	7	4	8	2	3	10	11	9	6	105
105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105

(B)														105
1	13	10	14	11	6	7	9	8	3	4	2	12	5	105
4	2	13	1	14	7	8	10	9	5	3	12	6	11	105
6	5	3	13	2	8	9	1	10	4	12	7	11	14	105
5	7	6	4	13	9	10	2	1	12	8	11	14	3	105
12	6	8	7	5	10	1	3	2	9	11	14	4	13	105
9	10	1	2	3	11	14	12	13	8	7	6	5	4	105
2	3	4	5	6	13	12	14	11	1	10	9	8	7	105
3	4	5	6	7	14	11	13	12	2	1	10	9	8	105
7	8	9	10	1	12	13	11	14	6	5	4	3	2	105
13	9	14	11	4	5	6	8	7	10	2	3	1	12	105
8	14	11	3	12	4	5	7	6	13	9	1	2	10	105
14	11	2	12	9	3	4	6	5	7	13	8	10	1	105
11	1	12	8	10	2	3	5	4	14	6	13	7	9	105
10	12	7	9	8	1	2	4	3	11	14	5	13	6	105
105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105	105

By application of the formula $14 \times (A - 1) + B$, we get the magic square given in Example 3.2.

Grid 1. Let's write the above Latin squares in terms of a Grid representing the numbers in alphabets:

a	g	n	h	j	f	e	c	b	l	k	m	i	d
k	b	h	m	n	j	g	i	a	d	e	f	c	l
i	l	c	j	m	e	f	a	d	b	g	h	k	n
n	h	k	d	l	i	a	f	c	m	b	g	j	e
l	f	d	a	i	g	c	h	j	e	m	b	n	k
h	a	g	c	b	l	m	k	n	f	d	j	e	i
b	c	j	e	a	k	n	l	m	g	i	d	f	h
d	e	f	g	c	n	k	m	l	i	j	a	h	b
c	d	e	f	g	m	l	n	k	h	a	i	b	j
e	k	l	b	f	d	h	g	i	j	n	c	a	m
f	n	m	i	e	b	j	d	g	a	h	k	l	c
j	m	a	l	k	h	i	b	f	n	c	e	d	g
m	j	i	n	d	c	b	e	h	k	f	l	g	a
g	i	b	k	h	a	d	j	e	c	l	n	m	f
							A						

a	k	i	n	l	h	b	d	c	e	f	j	m	g
g	b	l	h	f	a	c	e	d	k	n	m	j	i
n	h	c	k	d	g	j	f	e	l	m	a	i	b
h	m	j	d	a	c	e	g	f	b	i	l	n	k
j	n	m	l	i	b	a	c	g	f	e	k	d	h
f	j	e	i	g	l	k	n	m	d	b	h	c	a
e	g	f	a	c	m	n	k	l	h	j	i	b	d
c	i	a	f	h	k	l	m	n	g	d	b	e	j
b	a	d	c	j	n	m	l	k	i	g	f	h	e
l	d	b	m	e	f	g	i	h	j	a	n	k	c
k	e	g	b	m	d	i	j	a	n	h	c	f	l
m	f	h	g	b	j	d	a	i	c	k	e	l	n
i	c	k	j	n	e	f	h	b	a	l	d	g	m
d	l	n	e	k	i	h	b	j	m	c	g	a	f
							B						

For more details refer author's work [46]

3.2 Perfect Square Entries Sum

Below are five different magic squares of order 14 resulting in **uniformity**, **Pythagorean triples** and **minimum perfect square sum** properties. Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

3.2.1 Uniformity Property

Example 3.2. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{1, 3, \dots, 389, 391\}$, a magic square of order 14 is given by

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													2744	
1	189	381	223	275	155	115	63	33	317	291	355	249	97	2744	
293	31	219	351	375	253	173	233	7	105	139	165	75	325	2744	
251	323	61	273	343	125	159	11	93	51	193	197	297	367	2744	
379	221	299	91	309	229	9	153	67	339	45	191	279	133	2744	
327	167	109	23	241	171	57	201	265	123	345	49	371	295	2744	
207	19	177	73	41	331	357	307	389	147	87	267	117	225	2744	
37	69	263	113	5	305	391	329	359	183	243	101	143	203	2744	
89	129	141	179	71	385	303	361	335	237	259	3	205	47	2744	
59	85	119	145	187	363	333	387	301	213	13	235	43	261	2744	
135	287	311	53	149	95	209	185	239	271	365	83	21	341	2744	
161	373	349	227	137	35	269	103	169	27	211	285	319	79	2744	
277	347	15	321	283	215	231	29	157	369	77	121	107	195	2744	
353	257	245	383	111	65	39	127	199	281	163	315	181	25	2744	
175	247	55	289	217	17	99	255	131	81	313	377	337	151	2744	
2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744

Example 3.3. For the consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{197/2, 199/2, \dots, 583/2, 587/2\}$, a magic square of order 14 is given by

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													2744
98.5	192.5	288.5	209.5	235.5	175.5	155.5	129.5	114.5	256.5	243.5	275.5	222.5	146.5	2744
244.5	113.5	207.5	273.5	285.5	224.5	184.5	214.5	101.5	150.5	167.5	180.5	135.5	260.5	2744
223.5	259.5	128.5	234.5	269.5	160.5	177.5	103.5	144.5	123.5	194.5	196.5	246.5	281.5	2744
287.5	208.5	247.5	143.5	252.5	212.5	102.5	174.5	131.5	267.5	120.5	193.5	237.5	164.5	2744
261.5	181.5	152.5	109.5	218.5	183.5	126.5	198.5	230.5	159.5	270.5	122.5	283.5	245.5	2744
201.5	107.5	186.5	134.5	118.5	263.5	276.5	251.5	292.5	171.5	141.5	231.5	156.5	210.5	2744
116.5	132.5	229.5	154.5	100.5	250.5	293.5	262.5	277.5	189.5	219.5	148.5	169.5	199.5	2744
142.5	162.5	168.5	187.5	133.5	290.5	249.5	278.5	265.5	216.5	227.5	99.5	200.5	121.5	2744
127.5	140.5	157.5	170.5	191.5	279.5	264.5	291.5	248.5	204.5	104.5	215.5	119.5	228.5	2744
165.5	241.5	253.5	124.5	172.5	145.5	202.5	190.5	217.5	233.5	280.5	139.5	108.5	268.5	2744
178.5	284.5	272.5	211.5	166.5	115.5	232.5	149.5	182.5	111.5	203.5	240.5	257.5	137.5	2744
236.5	271.5	105.5	258.5	239.5	205.5	213.5	112.5	176.5	282.5	136.5	158.5	151.5	195.5	2744
274.5	226.5	220.5	289.5	153.5	130.5	117.5	161.5	197.5	238.5	179.5	255.5	188.5	110.5	2744
185.5	221.5	125.5	242.5	206.5	106.5	147.5	225.5	163.5	138.5	254.5	286.5	266.5	173.5	2744
2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744	2744

In both the Examples 3.2 and 3.3, the magic sums are equal. See below:

$$S_{14 \times 14} = 2744 = 14^3; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 2744 = 38416 = 196^2 = 14^4.$$

The magic squares given in Examples 3.2 and 3.3 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 14, 14^2, 14^3, 14^4 \rangle$.

3.2.2 Pythagorean Triple

Example 3.4. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{61, 63, \dots, 449, 451\}$, a magic square of order 14 is given by

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													3584	
61	249	441	283	335	215	175	123	93	377	351	415	309	157	3584	
353	91	279	411	435	313	233	293	67	165	199	225	135	385	3584	
311	383	121	333	403	185	219	71	153	111	253	257	357	427	3584	
439	281	359	151	369	289	69	213	127	399	105	251	339	193	3584	
387	227	169	83	301	231	117	261	325	183	405	109	431	355	3584	
267	79	237	133	101	391	417	367	449	207	147	327	177	285	3584	
97	129	323	173	65	365	451	389	419	243	303	161	203	263	3584	
149	189	201	239	131	445	363	421	395	297	319	63	265	107	3584	
119	145	179	205	247	423	393	447	361	273	73	295	103	321	3584	
195	347	371	113	209	155	269	245	299	331	425	143	81	401	3584	
221	433	409	287	197	95	329	163	229	87	271	345	379	139	3584	
337	407	75	381	343	275	291	89	217	429	137	181	167	255	3584	
413	317	305	443	171	125	99	187	259	341	223	375	241	85	3584	
235	307	115	349	277	77	159	315	191	141	373	437	397	211	3584	
3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584

Example 3.5. For the consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{317/2, 319/2, \dots, 705/2, 707/2\}$, a magic square of order 14 is given by

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													3584
158.5	252.5	348.5	269.5	295.5	235.5	215.5	189.5	174.5	316.5	303.5	335.5	282.5	206.5	3584
304.5	173.5	267.5	333.5	345.5	284.5	244.5	274.5	161.5	210.5	227.5	240.5	195.5	320.5	3584
283.5	319.5	188.5	294.5	329.5	220.5	237.5	163.5	204.5	183.5	254.5	256.5	306.5	341.5	3584
347.5	268.5	307.5	203.5	312.5	272.5	162.5	234.5	191.5	327.5	180.5	253.5	297.5	224.5	3584
321.5	241.5	212.5	169.5	278.5	243.5	186.5	258.5	290.5	219.5	330.5	182.5	343.5	305.5	3584
261.5	167.5	246.5	194.5	178.5	323.5	336.5	311.5	352.5	231.5	201.5	291.5	216.5	270.5	3584
176.5	192.5	289.5	214.5	160.5	310.5	353.5	322.5	337.5	249.5	279.5	208.5	229.5	259.5	3584
202.5	222.5	228.5	247.5	193.5	350.5	309.5	338.5	325.5	276.5	287.5	159.5	260.5	181.5	3584
187.5	200.5	217.5	230.5	251.5	339.5	324.5	351.5	308.5	264.5	164.5	275.5	179.5	288.5	3584
225.5	301.5	313.5	184.5	232.5	205.5	262.5	250.5	277.5	293.5	340.5	199.5	168.5	328.5	3584
238.5	344.5	332.5	271.5	226.5	175.5	292.5	209.5	242.5	171.5	263.5	300.5	317.5	197.5	3584
296.5	331.5	165.5	318.5	299.5	265.5	273.5	172.5	236.5	342.5	196.5	218.5	211.5	255.5	3584
334.5	286.5	280.5	349.5	213.5	190.5	177.5	221.5	257.5	298.5	239.5	315.5	248.5	170.5	3584
245.5	281.5	185.5	302.5	266.5	166.5	207.5	285.5	223.5	198.5	314.5	346.5	326.5	233.5	3584
3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584	3584

In both the Examples 3.4 and 3.5, the magic sums are equal. See below:

$$S_{14 \times 14} = 3584; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 3584 = 50176 = 224^2.$$

The magic squares of order 14 given in Examples 3.4 and 3.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (30, 224, 226)**, i.e., $30^2 + 224^2 = 226^2$ with least possible entries resulting in **perfect square sum**.

3.2.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Example 3.6. For the consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$, a magic square of order 14 is given by

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													1400
2.5	96.5	192.5	113.5	139.5	79.5	59.5	33.5	18.5	160.5	147.5	179.5	126.5	50.5	1400
148.5	17.5	111.5	177.5	189.5	128.5	88.5	118.5	5.5	54.5	71.5	84.5	39.5	164.5	1400
127.5	163.5	32.5	138.5	173.5	64.5	81.5	7.5	48.5	27.5	98.5	100.5	150.5	185.5	1400
191.5	112.5	151.5	47.5	156.5	116.5	6.5	78.5	35.5	171.5	24.5	97.5	141.5	68.5	1400
165.5	85.5	56.5	13.5	122.5	87.5	30.5	102.5	134.5	63.5	174.5	26.5	187.5	149.5	1400
105.5	11.5	90.5	38.5	22.5	167.5	180.5	155.5	196.5	75.5	45.5	135.5	60.5	114.5	1400
20.5	36.5	133.5	58.5	4.5	154.5	197.5	166.5	181.5	93.5	123.5	52.5	73.5	103.5	1400
46.5	66.5	72.5	91.5	37.5	194.5	153.5	182.5	169.5	120.5	131.5	3.5	104.5	25.5	1400
31.5	44.5	61.5	74.5	95.5	183.5	168.5	195.5	152.5	108.5	8.5	119.5	23.5	132.5	1400
69.5	145.5	157.5	28.5	76.5	49.5	106.5	94.5	121.5	137.5	184.5	43.5	12.5	172.5	1400
82.5	188.5	176.5	115.5	70.5	19.5	136.5	53.5	86.5	15.5	107.5	144.5	161.5	41.5	1400
140.5	175.5	9.5	162.5	143.5	109.5	117.5	16.5	80.5	186.5	40.5	62.5	55.5	99.5	1400
178.5	130.5	124.5	193.5	57.5	34.5	21.5	65.5	101.5	142.5	83.5	159.5	92.5	14.5	1400
89.5	125.5	29.5	146.5	110.5	10.5	51.5	129.5	67.5	42.5	158.5	190.5	170.5	77.5	1400
1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400	1400

The entries are with **minimum perfect square sum**.

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1400; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 1400 = 19600 = 140^2.$$

For more details refer author's work [14, 15, 16, 17, 18]

3.3 Upside-Down, Mirror Looking and Water Reflection

Let's consider the following image:

Source: <https://www.mathsisfun.com/definitions/vertical-flip.html>

From the above image we understand that **horizontal flip** is same as **mirror looking image** and the **vertical flip** is same as **water reflection image**. The same terms are given in **paint brush of microsoft**. Let's see how it works on numbers.

Let's consider following 9 digits written in digital form:

0-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9

- **180° Rotation**

6-8-1-9-5-4-6-2-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 where the number 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6. Thus the **survival numbers** after 180° rotation are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9. Sometimes we call them as **upside-down** numbers.

- **Mirror Looking**

It is same as **horizontal flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

2-8-1-2-2-4-6-5-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **horizontal flip** are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8. Sometimes we call them as **mirror-looking** numbers.

- **Water Reflection**

It is same as **vertical flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

0-1-5-3-4-2-2-1-8-2

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **vertical flip** are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. For the first time we call these numbers as **water reflection** or **water reflexive** numbers.

We observe that the numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are in all the three situations, i.e., these are **upside-down**, **mirror-looking** and **water reflexive**. We call them as **universal numbers** provided they are written in **digital form**. There left only one number 3. It is only **water reflexive**. While the numbers 6 and 9 are only **upside-down**.

There is a lot of work by author on **upside-down** and **mirror-looking** numbers. This work is concentrated only towards magic squares having **water reflexive** numbers, i.e., 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. The numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are already studied previously. This work brings magic squares of order 14 to 16 specially in number 3 along with 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8.

3.3.1 Upside-Down and Mirror Looking

- 4-Digits Cell Entries

Below are two examples of upside-down and/or mirror looking magic squares of order 14 with four digits (0,2,5,8) and (1,6,8,9).

Example 3.7.

0000	2880	8855	5088	5882	2250	2002	0508	0205	8220	8022	8558	5585	0828
8028	0202	5082	8550	8822	5800	2805	5520	0008	0880	2088	2285	0558	8255
5588	8250	0505	5880	8508	2028	2258	0022	0820	0282	2885	5000	8055	8802
8850	5085	8058	0808	8200	5505	0020	2228	0522	8502	0255	2882	5888	2080
8258	2288	0885	0082	5555	2802	0500	5005	5828	2022	8520	0280	8808	8050
5022	0058	2820	0555	0228	8282	8580	8088	8885	2208	0802	5850	2005	5500
0220	0528	5822	2000	0005	8085	8888	8280	8582	2850	5558	0855	2202	5008
0805	2055	2200	2822	0550	8880	8082	8585	8288	5528	5808	0002	5020	0258
0502	0800	2008	2205	2858	8588	8285	8882	8080	5055	0028	5522	0250	5820
2082	8008	8202	0285	2220	0822	5028	2855	5550	5858	8800	0588	0080	8505
2280	8820	8528	5502	2085	0208	5855	0858	2800	0088	5050	8005	8222	0582
5885	8522	0050	8228	8002	5058	5508	0200	2255	8805	0580	2020	0882	2888
8555	5805	5580	8858	0888	0520	0222	2050	5002	8000	2282	8208	2828	0085
2808	5582	0288	8020	5080	0055	0850	5802	2058	0585	8205	8828	8500	2222

This Example 3.29 is *upside-down and mirror looking* with magic sum, $S_{14 \times 14}(0, 2, 5, 8) := 58883$.

Example 3.8.

1111	6991	9988	8699	8996	6886	6616	1961	1619	9666	9168	9889	8898	6169
9169	1616	8696	9886	9968	8911	6919	8866	1161	6191	6699	6898	1989	9688
8899	9686	1919	8991	9861	6669	6889	1168	6166	1696	6998	8611	9188	9916
9986	8698	9189	6161	9611	8819	1166	6869	1968	9816	1688	6996	8999	6691
9689	6899	6198	1196	8888	6916	1911	8619	8969	6668	9866	1691	9961	9186
8668	1189	6966	1988	1669	9696	9891	9199	9998	6861	6116	8986	6619	8811
1666	1969	8968	6611	1119	9198	9999	9691	9896	6986	8889	6188	6816	8661
6119	6688	6811	6968	1986	9991	9196	9898	9699	8869	8961	1116	8666	1689
1916	6111	6661	6819	6989	9899	9698	9996	9191	8688	1169	8868	1686	8966
6696	9161	9616	1698	6866	6168	8669	6988	8886	8989	9911	1999	1191	9819
6891	9966	9869	8816	6698	1661	8988	6189	6911	1199	8686	9119	9668	1996
8998	9868	1186	9669	9116	8689	8861	1611	6888	9919	1991	6666	6196	6999
9888	8919	8891	9989	6199	1966	1668	6686	8616	9111	6896	9661	6969	1198
6961	8896	1699	9166	8691	1188	6186	8916	6689	1998	9619	9969	9811	6868

This Example 3.30 is only *upside-down* with magic sum, $S_{14 \times 14}(1, 6, 8, 9) := 96657$.

• **6-Digits Cell Entries**

Below are two examples of upside-down and/or mirror looking magic squares of order 14 with three digits (1,6,9) and (2,5,8)

Example 3.9.

222222	555828	885588	558885	822858	552558	522225	255288	225255	858522	828552	882822	588882	288555
828555	225225	558858	882558	885552	822222	555255	588522	222288	288828	522885	552882	255822	858588
588885	858558	255255	822828	882288	522555	552822	222552	288522	225858	555882	558222	828588	885225
885558	558882	828822	288288	858222	588255	222522	552555	255552	882225	225588	555858	822885	522828
858822	552885	288882	222858	588588	555225	255222	558255	822555	522552	882522	225828	885288	828558
558552	222822	555522	255588	225555	858858	882828	828885	885882	552288	288225	822558	522255	588222
225522	255555	822552	522222	222255	828882	885885	858828	882858	555558	588822	288588	552225	558288
288255	522588	552222	555552	255558	885828	828858	882882	858885	588555	822288	222225	558522	225822
255225	288222	522288	552255	555822	882885	858882	885858	828828	558588	222555	588552	225558	822522
522858	828288	858225	225882	552522	288552	558555	555588	588558	822822	885222	255885	222828	882255
552828	885522	882555	588225	522882	225288	822588	288822	555222	222885	558558	828255	858552	255858
822882	882552	222558	858555	828225	558822	588288	225222	552588	885255	255828	522522	288858	555885
882588	822255	588828	885822	288885	255522	225552	522558	558225	828222	552858	858288	555555	222882
555288	588858	225885	828522	558828	222588	288558	822225	522822	255882	858255	885555	882222	552552

This Example 3.9 is *upside-down and mirror looking* with magic sum $S_{14 \times 14}(2, 5, 8) := 8048040$.

Example 3.10.

116116	669966	999911	699999	919991	666699	616119	166611	119166	991616	966666	996919	911996	611669
966669	119119	699991	996699	999666	919116	669166	911616	116611	611966	616999	666996	166919	991911
911999	991699	166166	919966	996611	616669	666919	116666	611616	119991	669996	699116	966911	999119
999699	699996	966919	611611	991116	911166	116616	666669	166666	996119	119911	669991	919999	616966
991919	666999	611996	116991	911911	669119	166116	699166	919669	616666	996616	119966	999611	966699
699666	116919	669616	166911	119669	991991	996966	966999	999996	666611	611119	919699	616166	911116
119616	166669	919666	616116	116166	966996	999999	991966	996991	669699	911919	611911	666119	699611
611166	616911	666116	669666	166699	999966	966991	996996	991999	911669	919611	116119	699616	119919
166119	611116	616611	666166	669919	996999	991996	999991	966966	699911	116669	911666	119699	919616
616991	966611	991119	119996	666616	611666	699669	669911	911699	919919	999116	166999	116966	996166
666966	999616	996669	911119	616996	119611	919911	611919	669116	116999	699699	966166	991666	166991
919996	996666	116699	991669	966119	699919	911611	119116	666911	999166	166966	616616	611991	669999
996911	919166	911966	999919	611999	166616	119666	616699	699119	966116	666991	991611	669669	116996
669611	911991	119999	966616	699966	116911	611699	919119	616919	166996	991166	999669	996116	666666

This Example 3.10 is only *upside-down* with magic sum, $S_{14 \times 14}(1, 6, 9) := 9453444$.

• **8-Digits Cell**

Below are three examples of upside-down and/or mirror looking magic squares of order 14 with two digits (1,8), (2,5) and (6,9)

Example 3.11.

88818881	81881181	18111818	81811118	18881811	88188118	18818111	88111881	81111888	11188811	11888188	11818818	81181188	18188181
11188188	88188818	81811181	18118881	81181118	88118111	18181888	81881818	18881881	11888181	11818811	81111188	88818118	18811811
11888118	11188181	88118811	81181181	18118818	81881888	88811881	81818881	18811818	11818188	18881188	88188111	18181811	81111118
11818181	11888111	11188118	81888188	81111181	81811881	88181818	81188818	18188881	18811188	88111888	88811811	18881118	18118811
18181188	11818118	11881888	11188111	81818181	81181818	88118881	81118811	88818818	81881881	88181811	18811118	18118188	18881181
81111881	18881818	18818881	18188818	88818811	18111811	11811118	11181188	11881181	81181888	81818111	81888118	88118181	88188188
18818818	18188811	88818188	88188181	88118118	11181181	11881188	18111118	11811811	18888881	81111818	81181881	81811888	81888111
81188811	81118188	18888181	18818118	18188111	11881118	11181811	11811181	18111188	81818818	81888881	88111818	88181881	88811888
18888111	18811888	18181881	88811818	88188881	11811188	18111181	11881811	11181118	81118118	81188181	81818188	81888811	88118818
88111181	18111881	81881118	81111811	18818188	88818181	18888118	88181888	81188111	18181818	11188818	11888811	11818881	81811188
18111888	88111118	81181811	18888811	81881188	18188188	81118181	88818111	81818118	88181181	18811881	11188881	11888818	11811818
88181118	81811811	81118818	88111188	11811881	18818811	81188188	18188118	81888181	18118111	88811181	18881888	11181818	11888881
81881811	81188881	88181188	11811888	11881818	18888818	81818811	18818181	88118188	88811118	18118118	18181181	81118111	11181881
81811818	88811188	11818111	11881881	11181888	81118881	81888818	18888188	88188811	88111811	18181118	18118181	18811181	81188118

This Example 3.11 is *upside-down and mirror looking* with magic sum $S_{14 \times 14}(1, 8) := 699999993$. The internal block is a magic square of order 4.

Example 3.12.

22222222	25525255	55555225	52255555	52555522	25255222	25222225	22522522	22252255	55252525	55222552	55525252	52525552	22552555
55222555	22252225	52255522	55525222	55552552	52552222	25522255	52522525	22222522	22555255	25225555	25255552	22525252	55255225
52525555	55255222	22522255	52555255	55522522	25222555	25255252	22222552	22552525	22255522	25525552	52252222	55225225	55552225
55555222	52255552	55225252	22552522	55252222	52522255	22222525	25252555	22522552	55522225	22255225	25525522	52555555	25225255
55255252	25255555	22555552	22225522	52525225	25522225	22522222	52252255	52552555	25222552	55522525	22255255	55552522	55225222
52252552	22225252	25522525	22525225	22252555	55255522	55525255	55225555	55555552	25252522	22552225	52555222	25222255	52522222
22252525	22522555	52552552	25222222	22222255	55225552	55555555	55255255	55525522	25525222	52525252	22555225	25252225	52252522
22552255	25225225	25252222	25522552	22525222	55555255	55225522	55525552	55255555	52522555	52552522	22222225	52252525	22255252
22522225	22552222	25222522	25252255	25525252	55525555	55255552	55555522	55225255	52255225	22222555	52522552	22255222	52552525
25225522	55222522	55252225	22255552	25252525	22552552	52252555	25525225	52525222	52555252	55552222	22255555	22225255	55522255
25255255	55552525	55522555	52522225	25225552	22252522	52555225	22555252	25522222	22225555	52255222	55222255	55252552	22525522
52555552	55522552	22225222	55252555	55222225	52255252	52522522	22252222	25255225	55552255	22525255	25222525	22555522	25525555
55525225	52552255	52525255	55555252	22555555	22522525	22252552	25225222	52252225	55222222	25255522	55252522	25522555	22225552
25522522	52525522	22255555	55222525	52255255	22225225	22555222	52552225	25225252	22525552	55252255	55552555	55522222	25252552

This Example 3.12 is *upside-down and mirror looking* with magic sum $S_{14 \times 14}(2, 5) := 544444439$. The internal block is a magic square of order 4.

Example 3.13.

99969996	96996696	69666969	96966669	69996966	99699669	69969666	99666996	96666999	66699966	66999699	66969969	96696699	69699696
66699699	99699969	96966696	69669996	96696669	99669666	69696999	96996969	69996996	66999696	66969966	96666699	99969669	69966966
66999669	66699696	99669966	96696696	69669969	96996999	99966996	96969996	69966969	66969699	69996699	99699666	69696966	96666669
66969696	66999666	66699669	96999699	96666696	96966996	99696969	96699969	69699996	69966699	99666999	99966966	69996669	69669966
69696699	66969669	66996999	66699666	96969696	96696969	99669996	96669966	99969969	96996996	99696966	69966669	69669699	69996696
96666996	69996969	69969996	69699969	99969966	69666966	66966669	66696699	66996696	96696999	96969666	96999669	99669696	99699699
69969969	69699966	99969699	99699696	99669669	66696696	66996699	69666669	66966966	69999996	96666969	96696996	96966999	96999666
96699966	96669699	69999696	69969669	69699666	66996669	66696966	66966696	69666699	96969969	96999996	99666969	99696996	99966999
69999666	69966999	69696996	99966969	99699996	66966699	69666696	66996966	66696669	96669669	96699696	96969699	96999966	99669969
99666696	69666996	96996669	96666966	69969699	99969696	69999669	99696999	96699666	69696969	66699969	66999966	66969996	96966699
69666999	99666669	96696966	69999966	96996699	69699699	96669696	99969666	96969669	99696696	69966996	66699996	66999969	66966969
99696669	96966966	96669969	99666699	66966996	69969966	96699699	69699669	96999696	69669666	99966696	69996999	66696969	66999996
96996966	96699996	99696699	66966999	66996969	69999969	96969966	69969696	99669699	99966669	69669669	69696966	96669666	66696996
96966969	99966699	66969666	66996996	66696999	96669996	96999969	69999699	99699966	99666966	69696669	69669696	69966696	96699669

This Example 3.13 is only *upside-down* with magic sum $S_{14 \times 14}(6,9) := 1166666655$. The internal block is a magic square of order 4.

For more details refer author's work [46, 47].

3.3.2 Water Reflection

- 4-Digits Magic Squares

In this subsection we shall bring four magic squares of order 14 of 4-digits (2,3,5,8), (1,2,3,5), (0,2,3,5) and (0,1,3,8).

Example 3.14. *Let's consider a magic square of order 14 with 4-digits (2,3,5,8) given by*

2222	3558	8853	5288	5582	3352	3223	2528	2325	8232	5833	8555	5385	2835
5835	2323	5282	8552	8833	5522	3525	5332	2228	2858	3288	3385	2555	8253
5388	8252	2525	5558	8528	3235	3355	2233	2832	2382	3585	5222	5853	8823
8852	5285	5855	2828	8222	5325	2232	3335	2533	8523	2353	3582	5588	3258
8255	3388	2885	2282	5353	3523	2522	5225	5535	3233	8532	2358	8828	5852
5233	2255	3532	2553	2335	8282	8558	5888	8885	3328	2823	5552	3225	5322
2332	2535	5533	3222	2225	5885	8888	8258	8582	3552	5355	2853	3323	5228
2825	3253	3322	3533	2552	8858	5882	8585	8288	5335	5528	2223	5232	2355
2523	2822	3228	3325	3555	8588	8285	8882	5858	5253	2235	5333	2352	5532
3282	5828	8223	2385	3332	2833	5235	3553	5352	5555	8822	2588	2258	8525
3358	8832	8535	5323	3285	2328	5553	2855	3522	2288	5252	5825	8233	2582
5585	8533	2252	8235	5823	5255	5328	2322	3353	8825	2558	3232	2882	3588
8553	5525	5358	8855	2888	2532	2333	3252	5223	5822	3382	8228	3535	2285
3528	5382	2388	5832	5258	2253	2852	5523	3255	2585	8225	8835	8522	3333

The above magic square of order 14 with digits is (2,3,5,8) is water reflexive. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 3.15. *Let's replace in Example 3.14, we get*

2222	3551	1153	5211	5512	3352	3223	2521	2325	1232	5133	1555	5315	2135
5135	2323	5212	1552	1133	5522	3525	5332	2221	2151	3211	3315	2555	1253
5311	1252	2525	5551	1521	3235	3355	2233	2132	2312	3515	5222	5153	1123
1152	5215	5155	2121	1222	5325	2232	3335	2533	1523	2353	3512	5511	3251
1255	3311	2115	2212	5353	3523	2522	5225	5535	3233	1532	2351	1121	5152
5233	2255	3532	2553	2335	1212	1551	5111	1115	3321	2123	5552	3225	5322
2332	2535	5533	3222	2225	5115	1111	1251	1512	3552	5355	2153	3323	5221
2125	3253	3322	3533	2552	1151	5112	1515	1211	5335	5521	2223	5232	2355
2523	2122	3221	3325	3555	1511	1215	1112	5151	5253	2235	5333	2352	5532
3212	5121	1223	2315	3332	2133	5235	3553	5352	5555	1122	2511	2251	1525
3351	1132	1535	5323	3215	2321	5553	2155	3522	2211	5252	5125	1233	2512
5515	1533	2252	1235	5123	5255	5321	2322	3353	1125	2551	3232	2112	3511
1553	5525	5351	1155	2111	2532	2333	3252	5223	5122	3312	1221	3535	2215
3521	5312	2311	5132	5251	2253	2152	5523	3255	2515	1225	1135	1522	3333

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(1, 2, 3, 5) := 44440$.

Example 3.16. *Let's replace in Example 3.14, we get*

2222	3550	0053	5200	5502	3352	3223	2520	2325	0232	5033	0555	5305	2035
5035	2323	5202	0552	0033	5522	3525	5332	2220	2050	3200	3305	2555	0253
5300	0252	2525	5550	0520	3235	3355	2233	2032	2302	3505	5222	5053	0023
0052	5205	5055	2020	0222	5325	2232	3335	2533	0523	2353	3502	5500	3250
0255	3300	2005	2202	5353	3523	2522	5225	5535	3233	0532	2350	0020	5052
5233	2255	3532	2553	2335	0202	0550	5000	0005	3320	2023	5552	3225	5322
2332	2535	5533	3222	2225	5005	0000	0250	0502	3552	5355	2053	3323	5220
2025	3253	3322	3533	2552	0050	5002	0505	0200	5335	5520	2223	5232	2355
2523	2022	3220	3325	3555	0500	0205	0002	5050	5253	2235	5333	2352	5532
3202	5020	0223	2305	3332	2033	5235	3553	5352	5555	0022	2500	2250	0525
3350	0032	0535	5323	3205	2320	5553	2055	3522	2200	5252	5025	0233	2502
5505	0533	2252	0235	5023	5255	5320	2322	3353	0025	2550	3232	2002	3500
0553	5525	5350	0055	2000	2532	2333	3252	5223	5022	3302	0220	3535	2205
3520	5302	2300	5032	5250	2253	2052	5523	3255	2505	0225	0035	0522	3333

The above sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(0, 2, 3, 5) := 41107$.

Example 3.17. *Let's replace in Example 3.14, we get*

1111	3880	0083	8100	8801	3381	3113	1810	1318	0131	8033	0888	8308	1038
8038	1313	8101	0881	0033	8811	3818	8331	1110	1080	3100	3308	1888	0183
8300	0181	1818	8880	0810	3138	3388	1133	1031	1301	3808	8111	8083	0013
0081	8108	8088	1010	0111	8318	1131	3338	1833	0813	1383	3801	8800	3180
0188	3300	1008	1101	8383	3813	1811	8118	8838	3133	0831	1380	0010	8081
8133	1188	3831	1883	1338	0101	0880	8000	0008	3310	1013	8881	3118	8311
1331	1838	8833	3111	1118	8008	0000	0180	0801	3881	8388	1083	3313	8110
1018	3183	3311	3833	1881	0080	8001	0808	0100	8338	8810	1113	8131	1388
1813	1011	3110	3318	3888	0800	0108	0001	8080	8183	1138	8333	1381	8831
3101	8010	0113	1308	3331	1033	8138	3883	8381	8888	0011	1800	1180	0818
3380	0031	0838	8313	3108	1310	8883	1088	3811	1100	8181	8018	0133	1801
8808	0833	1181	0138	8013	8188	8310	1311	3383	0018	1880	3131	1001	3800
0883	8818	8380	0088	1000	1831	1333	3181	8113	8011	3301	0110	3838	1108
3810	8301	1300	8031	8180	1183	1081	8813	3188	1808	0118	0038	0811	3333

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(0, 1, 3, 8) := 49995$.

Finally, we have four magic squares of order 14 with 4-digits (2,3,5,8), (1,2,3,5), (0,2,3,5) and (0,1,3,8) results in **water reflection** magic squares with same magic sums except the one with digits (0,1,3,8).

• **3-Digits Magic Squares**

In this subsection we shall bring four magic squares of order 14 of 3-digits (2,3,5), (1,3,8), (0,3,8) and (0,1,3).

Example 3.18. *Let's consider a magic square of order 14 with 3-digits (2,3,5) given by*

222222	332535	555522	335555	533552	322335	255225	232233	225232	552255	535322	553533	522553	233332
535332	225225	335552	553335	555322	533222	332232	522255	222233	233535	255555	322553	232533	552522
522555	552335	232232	533535	553233	255332	322533	222322	233255	225552	332553	335222	535522	555225
555335	335553	535533	233233	552222	522232	222255	322332	232322	553225	225522	332552	533555	255535
552533	322555	233553	222552	522522	332225	232222	335232	533332	255322	553255	225535	555233	535335
335322	222533	332255	232522	225332	552552	553535	535555	555553	322233	233225	533335	255232	522222
225255	232332	533322	255222	222232	535553	555555	552535	553552	332335	522533	233522	322225	335233
233232	255522	322222	332322	232335	555535	535552	553553	552555	522332	533233	222225	335255	225533
232225	233222	255233	322232	332533	553555	552553	555552	535535	335522	222332	522322	225335	533255
255552	535233	552225	225553	322255	233322	335332	332522	522335	533533	555222	232555	222535	553232
322535	555255	553332	522225	255553	225233	533522	233533	332222	222555	335335	535232	552322	232552
533553	553322	222335	552332	535225	335533	522233	225222	322522	555232	232535	255255	233552	332555
553522	533232	522535	555533	233555	232255	225322	255335	335225	535222	322552	552233	332332	222553
332233	522552	225555	535255	335535	222522	233335	533225	255533	232553	552232	555332	553222	322322

The above magic square of order 14 with digits is (2,3,5) is water reflexive with different magic sums. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 3.19. *Let's replace in Example 3.14, we get*

111111	331838	888811	338888	833881	311338	188118	131133	118131	881188	838311	883833	811883	133331
838331	118118	338881	883338	888311	833111	331131	811188	111133	133838	188888	311883	131833	881811
811888	881338	131131	833838	883133	188331	311833	111311	133188	118881	331883	338111	838811	888118
888338	338883	838833	133133	881111	811131	111188	311331	131311	883118	118811	331881	833888	188838
881833	311888	133883	111881	811811	331118	131111	338131	833331	188311	883188	118838	888133	838338
338311	111833	331188	131811	118331	881881	883838	838888	888883	311133	133118	833338	188131	811111
118188	131331	833311	188111	111131	838883	888888	881838	883881	331338	811833	133811	311118	338133
133131	188811	311111	331311	131338	888838	838881	883883	881888	811331	833133	111118	338188	118833
131118	133111	188133	311131	331833	883888	881883	888881	838838	338811	111331	811311	118338	833188
188881	838133	881118	118883	311188	133311	338331	331811	811338	833833	888111	131888	111838	883131
311838	888188	883331	811118	188883	118133	833811	133833	331111	111888	338338	838131	881311	131881
833883	883311	111338	881331	838118	338833	811133	118111	311811	888131	131838	188188	133881	331888
883811	833131	811838	888833	133888	131188	118311	188338	338118	838111	311881	881133	331331	111883
331133	811881	118888	838188	338838	111811	133338	833118	188833	131883	881131	888331	883111	311311

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(1, 3, 8) := 6801795$.

Example 3.20. *Let's replace in Example 3.18, we get*

000000	330838	888800	338888	833880	300338	088008	030033	008030	880088	838300	883833	800883	033330
838330	008008	338880	883338	888300	833000	330030	800088	000033	033838	088888	300883	030833	880800
800888	880338	030030	833838	883033	088330	300833	000300	033088	008880	330883	338000	838800	888008
888338	338883	838833	033033	880000	800030	000088	300330	030300	883008	008800	330880	833888	088838
880833	300888	033883	000880	800800	330008	030000	338030	833330	088300	883088	008838	888033	838338
338300	000833	330088	030800	008330	880880	883838	838888	888883	300033	033008	833338	88030	800000
008088	030330	833300	088000	000030	838883	888888	880838	883880	330338	800833	033800	300008	338033
033030	088800	300000	330300	030338	888838	838880	883883	880888	800330	833033	000008	338088	008833
030008	033000	088033	300030	330833	883888	880883	888880	838838	338800	000330	800300	008338	833088
088880	838033	880008	008883	300088	033300	338330	330800	800338	833833	888000	030888	000838	883030
300838	888088	883330	800008	088883	008033	833800	033833	330000	000888	338338	838030	880300	030880
833883	883300	000338	880330	838008	338833	800033	008000	300800	888030	030838	088088	033880	330888
883800	833030	800838	888833	033888	030088	008300	088338	338008	838000	300880	880033	330330	000883
330033	800880	008888	838088	338838	000800	033338	833008	088833	030883	880030	888330	883000	300300

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(0, 2, 8) := 6255249$.

Example 3.21. *Let's replace in Example 3.18, we get*

000000	330131	111100	331111	133110	300331	011001	030033	001030	110011	131300	113133	100113	033330
131330	001001	331110	113331	111300	133000	330030	100011	000033	033131	011111	300113	030133	110100
100111	110331	030030	133131	113033	011330	300133	000300	033011	001110	330113	331000	131100	111001
111331	331113	131133	33033	110000	100030	000011	300330	030300	113001	001100	330110	133111	011131
110133	300111	033113	000110	100100	330001	030000	331030	133330	011300	113011	001131	111033	131331
331300	000133	330011	030100	001330	110110	113131	131111	111113	300033	033001	133331	011030	100000
001011	030330	133300	011000	000030	131113	111111	110131	113110	330331	100133	033100	300001	331033
033030	011100	300000	330300	030331	111131	131110	113113	110111	100330	133033	000001	331011	001133
030001	033000	011033	300030	330133	113111	110113	111110	131131	331100	000330	100300	001331	133011
011110	131033	110001	001113	300011	033300	331330	330100	100331	133133	111000	030111	000131	113030
300131	111011	113330	100001	011113	001033	133100	033133	330000	000111	331331	131030	110300	030110
133113	113300	000331	110330	131001	331133	100033	001000	300100	111030	030131	011011	033110	330111
113100	133030	100131	111133	033111	030011	001300	011331	331001	131000	300110	110033	330330	000113
330033	100110	001111	131011	331131	000100	033331	133001	011133	030113	110030	111330	113000	300300

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(0, 1, 3) := 1735734$.

Finally, we have four magic squares of order 14 with 3-digits (2,3,5), (1,3,8), (0,3,8) and (0,1,3) results in **water reflection** magic squares with same magic sums except the first one with digits (2,3,5).

• **2-Digits Magic Squares**

In this subsection we shall bring three magic squares of order 14 of 2-digits (3,8), (1,3) and (0,3).

Example 3.22. *Let's consider a magic square of order 14 with 2-digits (3,8) given by*

88838883	83883383	38333838	83833338	38883833	88388338	38838333	88333883	83333888	33388833	33888388	33838838	83383388	38388383
33388388	88388838	83833383	38338883	83383338	88338333	38383888	83883838	38883883	33888383	33838833	83333388	88838338	38833833
33888338	33388383	88338833	83383383	38338838	83883888	88833883	83838883	38833838	33838388	38883388	88388333	38383833	83333338
33838383	33888333	33388338	83888388	83333383	83833883	88383838	83388838	38388883	38833388	88333888	88833833	38883338	38338833
38383388	33838338	33883888	33388333	83838383	83383838	88338883	83338833	88838838	83883883	88383833	38833338	38338388	38883383
83333883	38883838	38838883	38388838	88838833	38333833	33833338	33383388	33883383	83383888	83838333	83888338	88338383	88388388
38838838	38388833	88838388	88388383	88338338	33383383	33883388	38333338	33833833	38888883	83333838	83383883	83833888	83888333
83388833	83338388	38888383	38838338	38388333	33883338	33383833	33833383	38333388	83838838	83888883	88333838	88383883	88833888
38888333	38833888	38383883	88833838	88388883	33833388	38333383	33883833	33383338	83338338	83388383	83838388	83888833	88338838
88333383	38333883	83883338	83333833	38838388	88838383	38888338	88383888	83388333	38383838	33388838	33888833	33838883	83833388
38333888	88333338	83383833	38888833	83883388	38388388	83338383	88838333	83838338	88383383	38833883	33388883	33888838	33833838
88383338	83833833	83338838	88333388	33833883	38838833	83388388	38388338	83888383	38338333	88833383	38883888	33383838	33888883
83883833	83388883	88383388	33833888	33883838	38888838	83838833	38838383	88338388	88833338	38338338	38383383	83338333	33383883
83833838	88833388	33838333	33883883	33383888	83338883	83888838	38888388	88388833	88333833	38383338	38338383	38833383	83388338

Thus, the above magic square of order 14 with digits is (3,8) is *water reflexive* with different magic sums. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 3.23. *Let's replace in Example 3.22, we get*

11131113	13113313	31333131	13133331	31113133	11311331	31131333	11333113	13333111	33311133	33111311	33131131	13313311	31311313
33311311	11311131	13133313	31331113	13313331	11331333	31313111	13113131	31113113	33111313	33131133	13333311	11131331	31133133
33111331	33311313	11331133	13313313	31331131	13113111	11133113	13131113	31133131	33131311	31113311	11311333	31313133	13333331
33131313	33111333	33311331	13111311	13333313	13133113	11313131	13311131	31311113	31133311	11333111	11133133	31113331	31331133
31313311	33131331	33113111	33311333	13131313	13313131	11331113	13331133	11131131	13113113	11313133	31133331	31331311	31113313
13333113	31113131	31131113	31311131	11131133	31333133	33133331	33313311	33113313	13313111	13131333	13111331	11331313	11311311
31131131	31311133	11131311	11311313	11331331	33313313	33113311	31333331	33133133	31111113	13333131	13313113	13133111	13111333
13311133	13331311	31111313	31131331	31311333	33113331	33313133	33133313	31333311	13131131	13111113	11333131	11313113	11133111
31111333	31133111	31313113	11133131	11311113	33133311	31333313	33113133	33313331	13331331	13311313	13131311	13111133	11331131
11333313	31333113	13113331	13333133	31131311	11131313	31111331	11313111	13311333	31313131	33311131	33111133	33131113	13133311
31333111	11333331	13313133	31111133	13113311	31311311	13331313	11131333	13131331	11313313	31133113	33311113	33111131	33133131
11313331	13133133	13331131	11333311	33133113	31131133	13311311	31311331	13111313	31331333	11133313	31113111	33313131	33111113
13113133	13311113	11313311	33133111	33113131	31111131	13131133	31131313	11331311	11133331	31331331	31313313	13331333	33313113
13133131	11133311	33131333	33113113	33313111	13331113	13111131	31111311	11311133	11333133	31313331	31331313	31133313	13311331

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(1,3) := 311111108$.

Example 3.24. *Let's replace in Example 3.22, we get*

00030003	03003303	30333030	03033330	30003033	00300330	30030333	00333003	03333000	33300033	33000300	33030030	03303300	30300303
33300300	00300030	03033303	30330003	03303330	00330333	30303000	03003030	30003003	33000303	33030033	03333300	00030330	30033033
33000330	33300303	00330033	03303303	30330030	03003000	00033003	03030003	30033030	33030300	30003300	00300333	30303033	03333330
33030303	33000333	33300330	03000300	03333303	03033003	00303030	03300030	30300003	30033300	00333000	00033033	30003330	30330033
30303300	33030330	33003000	33300333	03030303	03303030	00330003	03330033	00030030	03003003	00303033	30033330	30330300	30003303
03333003	30003030	30030003	30300030	00030033	30333033	33033330	33303300	33003303	03303000	03030333	03000330	00330303	00300300
30030030	30300033	00030300	00300303	00330330	33303303	33003300	30333330	33033033	30000003	03333030	03303003	03033000	03000333
03300033	03330300	30000303	30030330	30300333	33003330	33303033	33033303	30333300	03030030	03000003	00333030	00303003	00033000
30000333	30033000	30303003	00033030	00300003	33033300	30333303	33003033	33303330	03330330	03300303	03030300	03000033	00330030
00333303	30333003	03003330	03333033	30030300	00030303	30000330	00303000	03300333	30303030	33300030	33000033	33030003	03033300
30333000	00333330	03303033	30000033	03003300	30300300	03330303	00030333	03030330	00303303	30033003	33300003	33000030	33033030
00303330	03033033	03330030	00333300	33033003	30030033	03300300	30300330	03000303	30330333	00033303	30003000	33303030	33000003
03003033	03300003	00303300	33033000	33003030	30000030	03030033	30030303	00330300	00033330	30330330	30303303	03330333	33303003
03033030	00033300	33030333	33003003	33303000	03330003	03000030	30000300	00300033	00333033	30303330	30330303	30033303	03300330

The above sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14}(0,3) := 233333331$.

Finally, we have four magic squares of order 14 with 2-digits (3,8), (1,3) and (0,3) results in **water reflection** magic squares with same magic sums.

For more details refer author's work [46].

3.4 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Square

Below are two result of a magic squares order 14 made in such a way that a magic square of order 12 is embedded in it.

Result 1. Below is an *algebraic magic square of order 14*

$(1/2)*S-A40$	$36*S-A52+A39+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A40-11*(7/2)*S$	$(1/2)*S-A29$	$(1/2)*S-A30$	$(1/2)*S-A31$	$(1/2)*S-A32$	$(1/2)*S-A33$	$(1/2)*S-A34$	$(1/2)*S-A35$	$(1/2)*S-A36$	$(1/2)*S-A37$	$(1/2)*S-A38$	$(1/2)*S-A39$	A52
$A52+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51-3*S$	$A3+A17-A21+A10-A13$	$A4+A6+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-2*A10+2*A13+A18+A20-A1$	$A23+A1-A24-2*A21+A28-A9-A27+A8+A25-A7-A11+A12-A6+2*A10-A13+A17+A5$	$A24+A21+A26+A9+A27-A8+A25+A7+A11-A18-A20-A12-A10-A4+S-A3-2*A17-A5-A23$	$A10+A3+A17-A25-A7$	$A22+A24+2*A21-A2-A28-A26+2*A7+A6-2*A10+A4-2*A17$	$A23-A19-A15-A24+A16-A21+A2-A9+A8-A25-2*A7+A20-A6+A10+A13+2*A17+A5$	$A19+A15-A22-A16-A21+A28+A26+A9-A8+2*A25+A7-A20-A13-A4+S-A3-A17-A5-A23$	A3	A4	A5	$S-A3-A4-A5$	$(7/2)*S-A52-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51$
$(1/2)*S-A41$	A1	$A28+A26+2*A25-A18-A20-A6+A10-A13-A4+S-A3-A17-A21$	$A24+A21-A28+A9+A27-A8-A25+A7+A11-A12+A6-A10+A3-A5-A23$	$A23-A1-A24-A26-A9-A27+A8-A25-A7-A11+A18+A20+A12+A13+A4+A17+A5$	A2	$A28+A26+A25-A7-A6+A10-A4+S-A3+A17-A22-A24-2*A21$	$A19+A15+A24-A16+A21+A9-A8+A7-A20+A6-A13+A3-A17-A5-A23$	$A23-A19-A15+A22+A16+A21-A2-A28-A26-A9+A8-A25+A20-A10+A13+A4+A5$	A6	$S-A3-A4-A6$	$A3-A5+A6$	$A4+A5-A6$	A41
$(1/2)*S-A42$	$A24+2*A21-A28+A9+A27-A8-A25+A7+A11-A12+A6-2*A10+A13+(1/2)*S-A17-A5-A23-A1$	$A23-A24-A21-A26-A9-A27+A8-A25-A7-A11+A18+A20+A12+A10+A4+(1/2)*S+A3+2*A17+A5$	$(1/2)*S-A3-A17+A21-A10+A13$	$(1/2)*S+A1-A4-A6-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+2*A10-2*A13-A18-A20$	$A19+A15+A24-A16+A21-A2+A9-A8+A25+2*A7-A20+A6-A10-A13+(1/2)*S-2*A17-A5-A23$	$A23-A19-A15+A22+A16+A21+A9-A8-A25-A7+A20+A13+A4-(1/2)*S+A3+A17+A5$	$(1/2)*S+A25+A7-A10-A3-A17$	$A2+A28+A26-2*A7-A6+2*A10-A4+(1/2)*S+2*A17-A22-A24-2*A21$	$S/2-A5$	$A3+A4+A5-S/2$	$S/2-A3$	$S/2-A4$	A42
$(1/2)*S-A43$	$A23-A24-A21+A28-A9-A27+A8+A25-A7-A11+A12-A6+A10+(1/2)*S-A3+A5$	$A1+A24+A26+A9+A27-A8+A25+A7+A11-A18-A20-A12-A13-A4+(1/2)*S-A17-A5-A23$	$S/2-A1$	$A21-A28-A26-2*A25+A18+A20+A6-A10+A13+A4-(1/2)*S+A3+A17$	$A23-A19-A15-A24+A16-A21-A9-A8-A7+A20-A6+A13+(1/2)*S-A3+A17+A5$	$A19+A15-A22-A16-A21+A2+A28+A26+A9-A8+A25-A20+A10-A13-A4+(1/2)*S-A5-A23$	$A22+A24+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-A12+A14-2*A10+2*A13$	$S+ A10-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+A12-A14-2*A13-A11$	$S/2-A3+A5-A6$	$S/2-A4-A5+A6$	$S/2-A6$	$A3+A4+A6-S/2$	A43
$(1/2)*S-A44$	A7	$A16-A28-A26-A9-2*A25-2*A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13+2*A17$	A8	$A28+A26+A9-A8+2*A25+A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+S-2*A17-A16$	A10	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-A12+A14-2*A10+2*A13$	A11	$S+ A10-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+A12-A14-2*A13-A11$	A13	A14	A15	$S-A13-A14-A15$	A44
$(1/2)*S-A45$	A9	$A28+A26+2*A25+A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+S-2*A17-A16$	$A7-A8+A9$	$A16-A28-A26-2*A9+A8-2*A25-2*A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13+2*A17$	A12	$S+ A10-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25-A14-2*A13$	$A10-A11+A12$	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-2*A12+A14-2*A10+2*A13+A11$	A16	$S-A13-A14-A16$	$A13-A15+A16$	$A14+A15-A16$	A45
$(1/2)*S-A46$	$S/2-A8$	$A16-A28-A26-A9+A8-2*A25-A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13-(1/2)*S+2*A17$	$S/2-A7$	$A28+A26+A9+2*A25+2*A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+(1/2)*S-2*A17-A16$	$S/2-A11$	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25-A12+A14+2*A13+A11-(1/2)*S-A10$	$S/2-A10$	$(1/2)*S-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+A12-A14+2*A10-2*A13$	$S/2-A15$	$A13+A14+A15-S/2$	$S/2-A13$	$S/2-A14$	A46
$(1/2)*S-A47$	$S/2-A7+A8-A9$	$A28+A26+2*A9-A8+2*A25+2*A7-A18-A20-A14-2*A13+(1/2)*S-2*A17-A16$	$S/2-A9$	$A16-A28-A26-2*A25-A7+A18+A20+A14+2*A13-(1/2)*S+2*A17$	$S/2-A10+A11-A12$	$(1/2)*S-A22-A24-A16-2*A21+A28+A26+2*A25+2*A12-A14+2*A10-2*A13-A11$	$S/2-A12$	$A22+A24+A16+2*A21-A28-A26-2*A25+2*A12+A14+2*A13-(1/2)*S-A10$	$S/2-A13+A15-A16$	$S/2-A14-A15+A16$	$S/2-A16$	$A13+A14+A16-S/2$	A47
$(1/2)*S-A48$	A17	A18	A19	$S-A17-A18-A19$	A21	A22	A23	$S-A21-A22-A23$	A25	A26	A27	$S-A25-A26-A27$	A48
$(1/2)*S-A49$	A20	$S-A17-A18-A20$	$A17-A19+A20$	$A18+A19-A20$	A24	$S-A21-A22-A24$	$A21-A23+A24$	$A22+A23-A24$	A28	$S-A25-A26-A28$	$A25-A27+A28$	$A26+A27-A28$	A49
$(1/2)*S-A50$	$S/2-A19$	$A17+A18+A19-S/2$	$S/2-A17$	$S/2-A18$	$S/2-A23$	$A21+A22+A23-S/2$	$S/2-A21$	$S/2-A22$	$S/2-A27$	$A25+A26+A27-S/2$	$S/2-A25$	$S/2-A26$	A50
$(1/2)*S-A51$	$S/2-A17+A19-A20$	$S/2-A18-A19+A20$	$S/2-A20$	$A17+A18+A20-S/2$	$S/2-A21+A23-A24$	$S/2-A22-A23+A24$	$S/2-A24$	$A21+A22+A24-S/2$	$S/2-A25+A27-A28$	$S/2-A26-A27+A28$	$S/2-A28$	$A25+A26+A28-S/2$	A51
$(1/2)*S-A52$	$3*S+A52-A39-A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A40$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40

• Details

It is a *single-digit bordered magic square of order 14* embedded with a *pandiagonal magic square of order 12*. It is composed of 9 equal sums *pandiagonal magic squares of order 4*. The letter *S* represents the magic sum of magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sum of order 14 is $\frac{7}{2} \times S$. We call it a *self-made* as it is complete in itself. Just choose values for A1 to A52 and the magic sum *S*, we always get a magic square of order 14. Sometimes we may call it as *algebraic magic square for reduced entries*. It requires only 52 entries instead of 196. To avoid decimal entries we need to choose even number for the magic sum of order 4. See below two examples:

Example 3.25. *Let's consider a magic square*

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													168
-25	341	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	61	168
571	5	0	9	34	7	11	7	23	12	13	14	9	-547	168
-26	10	33	6	-1	11	19	11	7	15	8	13	12	50	168
-27	15	-10	19	24	17	1	17	13	10	15	12	11	51	168
-28	18	25	14	-9	13	17	13	5	11	12	9	16	52	168
-29	16	10	17	5	19	17	20	-8	22	23	24	-21	53	168
-30	18	4	17	9	21	-9	20	16	25	-22	23	22	54	168
-31	7	19	8	14	4	32	5	7	0	45	2	1	55	168
-32	7	15	6	20	4	8	3	33	1	2	-1	46	56	168
-33	26	27	28	-33	30	31	32	-45	34	35	36	-57	57	168
-34	29	-34	27	26	33	-46	31	30	37	-58	35	34	58	168
-35	-4	57	-2	-3	-8	69	-6	-7	-12	81	-10	-11	59	168
-36	-3	-2	-5	58	-7	-6	-9	70	-11	-10	-13	82	60	168
-37	-317	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	168
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14} := 168$. The internal block is *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 48$

Example 3.26. *Let's consider a magic square*

mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	252									
-6	204	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	54	252
408	-2	-7	2	79	0	4	0	68	5	6	7	54	-372	252
-7	3	78	-1	-8	4	64	4	0	8	53	6	5	43	252
-8	34	-43	38	43	36	-32	36	32	29	-18	31	30	44	252
-9	37	44	33	-42	32	36	32	-28	30	31	28	-17	45	252
-10	9	3	10	50	12	10	13	37	15	16	17	24	46	252
-11	11	49	10	2	14	36	13	9	18	23	16	15	47	252
-12	26	-14	27	33	23	-1	24	26	19	12	21	20	48	252
-13	26	34	25	-13	23	27	22	0	20	21	18	13	49	252
-14	19	20	21	12	23	24	25	0	27	28	29	-12	50	252
-15	22	11	20	19	26	-1	24	23	30	-13	28	27	51	252
-16	15	24	17	16	11	36	13	12	7	48	9	8	52	252
-17	16	17	14	25	12	13	10	37	8	9	6	49	53	252
-18	-168	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	252
252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14} := 252$. The internal block is *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 72$

Result 2. Below is an *algebraic magic square of order 14*

$(1/2)*S-A66$	$36*S-A78+A65+A64+A63+A62+A61+A60+A59+A58+A57+A56+A55+A66-11*(7/2)*S$	$(1/2)*S-A55$	$(1/2)*S-A56$	$(1/2)*S-A57$	$(1/2)*S-A58$	$(1/2)*S-A59$	$(1/2)*S-A60$	$(1/2)*S-A61$	$(1/2)*S-A62$	$(1/2)*S-A63$	$(1/2)*S-A64$	$(1/2)*S-A65$	A78
$A78+A66+A67+A68+A69+A70+A71+A72+A73+A74+A75+A76+A77-3*S$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	A7	$A10+S-A12-A7$	$A12-A9-A10$	A9	A13	$A16+S-A18-A13$	$A18-A15-A16$	A15	$(7/2)*S-A78-A66-A67-A68-A69-A70-A71-A72-A73-A74-A75-A76-A77$
$(1/2)*S-A67$	A6	A4	A5	$S-A4-A5-A6$	A12	A10	A11	$S-A10-A11-A12$	A18	A16	A17	$S-A16-A17-A18$	A67
$(1/2)*S-A68$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$S-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$A8+A9-A12$	$A7+A8-A11$	$S-A7-A8-A10$	$A10+A11+A12-A8-A9$	$A14+A15-A18$	$A13+A14-A17$	$S-A13-A14-A16$	$A16+A17+A18-A14-A15$	A68
$(1/2)*S-A69$	$S-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$S-A7-A8-A9$	$A11-A8-2*A10+A12$	$A7+A8+A9+2*A10-A11-A12$	A8	$S-A13-A14-A15$	$A17-A14-2*A16+A18$	$A13+A14+A15+2*A16-A17-A18$	A14	A69
$(1/2)*S-A70$	A19	$A22+S-A24-A19$	$A24-A21-A22$	A21	A25	$A28+S-A30-A25$	$A30-A27-A28$	A27	A31	$A34+S-A36-A31$	$A36-A33-A34$	A33	A70
$(1/2)*S-A71$	A24	A22	A23	$S-A22-A23-A24$	A30	A28	A29	$S-A28-A29-A30$	A36	A34	A35	$S-A34-A35-A36$	A71
$(1/2)*S-A72$	$A20+A21-A24$	$A19+A20-A23$	$S-A19-A20-A22$	$A22+A23+A24-A20-A21$	$A26+A27-A30$	$A25+A26-A29$	$S-A25-A26-A28$	$A28+A29+A30-A26-A27$	$A32+A33-A36$	$A31+A32-A35$	$S-A31-A32-A34$	$A34+A35+A36-A32-A33$	A72
$(1/2)*S-A73$	$S-A19-A20-A21$	$A23-A20-2*A22+A24$	$A19+A20+A21+2*A22-A23-A24$	A20	$S-A25-A26-A27$	$A29-A26-2*A28+A30$	$A25+A26+A27+2*A28-A29-A30$	A26	$S-A31-A32-A33$	$A35-A32-2*A34+A36$	$A31+A32+A33+2*A34-A35-A36$	A32	A73
$(1/2)*S-A74$	A37	$A40+S-A42-A37$	$A42-A39-A40$	A39	A43	$A46+S-A48-A43$	$A48-A45-A46$	A45	A49	$A52+S-A54-A49$	$A54-A51-A52$	A51	A74
$(1/2)*S-A75$	A42	A40	A41	$S-A40-A41-A42$	A48	A46	A47	$S-A46-A47-A48$	A54	A52	A53	$S-A52-A53-A54$	A75
$(1/2)*S-A76$	$A38+A39-A42$	$A37+A38-A41$	$S-A37-A38-A40$	$A40+A41+A42-A38-A39$	$A44+A45-A48$	$A43+A44-A47$	$S-A43-A44-A46$	$A46+A47+A48-A44-A45$	$A50+A51-A54$	$A49+A50-A53$	$S-A49-A50-A52$	$A52+A53+A54-A50-A51$	A76
$(1/2)*S-A77$	$S-A37-A38-A39$	$A41-A38-2*A40+A42$	$A37+A38+A39+2*A40-A41-A42$	A38	$S-A43-A44-A45$	$A47-A44-2*A46+A48$	$A43+A44+A45+2*A46-A47-A48$	A44	$S-A49-A50-A51$	$A53-A50-2*A52+A54$	$A49+A50+A51+2*A52-A53-A54$	A50	A77
$(1/2)*S-A78$	$3*S+A78-A65-A64-A63-A62-A61-A60-A59-A58-A57-A56-A55-A66$	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	A60	A61	A62	A63	A64	A65	A66

• Details

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 14 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is composed of 9 equal sums magic squares of order 4. The letter S represents the magic sum of magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sum of order 14 is $\frac{7}{2} \times S$. We call it a **self-made** as it is complete in itself. Just choose values for A1 to A78 and the magic sum S, we always get a magic square of order 14. Sometimes we may call it as **algebraic magic square for reduced entries**. It requires only 78 entries instead of 196. To avoid decimal entries of magic square of order 14 we need to choose even number for the magic sum of order 4. See below two examples:

Example 3.27. Let's consider a magic square

mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												147	
-46	554	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	-41	-42	-43	-44	-45	79	147
823	2	38	-2	4	8	32	-8	10	14	26	-14	16	-802	147
-47	7	5	6	24	13	11	12	6	19	17	18	-12	68	147
-48	0	-1	32	11	6	5	14	17	12	11	-4	23	69	147
-49	33	0	6	3	15	-6	24	9	-3	-12	42	15	70	147
-50	20	20	-20	22	26	14	-26	28	32	8	-32	34	71	147
-51	25	23	24	-30	31	29	30	-48	37	35	36	-66	72	147
-52	18	17	-22	29	24	23	-40	35	30	29	-58	41	73	147
-53	-21	-18	60	21	-39	-24	78	27	-57	-30	96	33	74	147
-54	38	2	-38	40	44	-4	-44	46	50	-10	-50	52	75	147
-55	43	41	42	-84	49	47	48	-102	55	53	54	-120	76	147
-56	36	35	-76	47	42	41	-94	53	48	47	-112	59	77	147
-57	-75	-36	114	39	-93	-42	132	45	-111	-48	150	51	78	147
-58	-533	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	147
147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14} := 147$. The internal block is a magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 42$

Example 3.28. *Let's consider a magic square*

mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	182									
-41	529	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-35	-36	-37	-38	-39	-40	79	182
793	2	48	-2	4	8	42	-8	10	14	36	-14	16	-767	182
-42	7	5	6	34	13	11	12	16	19	17	18	-2	68	182
-43	0	-1	42	11	6	5	24	17	12	11	6	23	69	182
-44	43	0	6	3	25	-6	24	9	7	-12	42	15	70	182
-45	20	30	-20	22	26	24	-26	28	32	18	-32	34	71	182
-46	25	23	24	-20	31	29	30	-38	37	35	36	-56	72	182
-47	18	17	-12	29	24	23	-30	35	30	29	-48	41	73	182
-48	-11	-18	60	21	-29	-24	78	27	-47	-30	96	33	74	182
-49	38	12	-38	40	44	6	-44	46	50	0	-50	52	75	182
-50	43	41	42	-74	49	47	48	-92	55	53	54	-110	76	182
-51	36	35	-66	47	42	41	-84	53	48	47	###	59	77	182
-52	-65	-36	114	39	-83	-42	132	45	-101	-48	150	51	78	182
-53	-503	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	182
182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182	182

The magic sum of above magic square is $S_{14 \times 14} := 182$. The internal block is a magic square of order 12 formed by equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 52$

Remark 3.1. The different between two Results 1 and 2 is that in the first result the magic square of order 12 is *pandiagonal* with magic square of order 4 also *pandiagonal*, while in case of second result the magic squares of orders 12 and 4 are just magic square not *pandiagonal*. The second example allows us to bring magic square of order 14 with odd order sum without decimal entries.

For more studied toward this direction see the author's work [57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64].

3.5 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 14

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 14, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

3.5.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 3. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 14 in cyclic way is given by*

a40	a41	a42	a43	a44	a45	a46	a47	a48	a49	a50	$6*m-a44-a43-a42-a40-a41-a50-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49$	m-a51	a51
m-a40	m-a41	m-a42	m-a43	m-a44	m-a45	m-a46	m-a47	m-a48	m-a49	m-a50	$a44+a43+a42+a40+a41+a50+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49-5*m$	m-a52	a52
$6*m-a73-a75-a74-a77-a76-a78-a80-a79-a81-2*a72+a51-a52$	$a73+a75+a74+a77+a76+a78+a80+a79+a81+2*a72-a51+a52-5*m$	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	a20	$4*m-a14-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	m-a21	a21	m-a53	a53
a81	m-a81	m-a14	m-a15	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	m-a20	$a14+a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-3*m$	m-a22	a22	m-a54	a54
a80	m-a80	$4*m-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-2*a34+a21-a22$	$a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+2*a34-a21+a22-3*m$	$3*m-a2-a3-a1-a5-a4$	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	m-a23	a23	m-a55	a55
a79	m-a79	a39	m-a39	$a1+a5+a4+a2+a3-2*m$	m-a1	m-a2	m-a3	m-a4	m-a5	m-a24	a24	m-a56	a56
a78	m-a78	a38	m-a38	a6	a7	a8	$a8+3*m-2*a1+a12-a13-a2-a3-a5-a4$	$a5+a4+2*a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-a9-a6-a7-2*a8$	a9	m-a25	a25	m-a57	a57
a77	m-a77	a37	m-a37	m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	$a5+a4-a8+2*a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-2*m$	$m+a6+a7+2*a8-a5-a4-2*a1+a12-a13-a2-a3+a9$	m-a9	m-a26	a26	m-a58	a58
a76	m-a76	a36	m-a36	$3*m-2*a1-2*a4+a10+a12-a13-a2-a3$	a10	$(2*a1+2*a4-2*a10-2*a12+a2+a3-a11)$	a11	a12	a13	m-a27	a27	m-a59	a59
a75	m-a75	a35	m-a35	$2*a1+2*a4-a10-a12+a13+a2+a3-2*m$	m-a10	$m-2*a1-2*a4+2*a10+2*a12-a2-a3+a11$	m-a11	m-a12	m-a13	$a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26+a27-3*m$	$4*m-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27$	m-a60	a60
a74	m-a74	a34	m-a34	$a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+2*a28-a14+a15-3*m$	m-a33	m-a32	m-a31	m-a30	m-a29	m-a28	$m+a14-a15-a28$	m-a61	a61
a73	m-a73	$a22+a34-a21$	$m+a21-a22-a34$	$4*m-a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-2*a28+a14-a15$	a33	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	$a15+a28-a14$	$a61+a60+a58+a59+a57+a55+a56+a54+a53+a51+a52-5*m$	$6*m-a61-a60-a58-a59-a57-a55-a56-a54-a53-a51-a52$
a72	m-a72	$a67+a68+2*a62+a66+a65+a64-a40+a41+a71+a70+a69+a63-5*m$	m-a71	m-a70	m-a69	m-a68	m-a67	m-a66	m-a65	m-a64	m-a63	m-a62	$m+a40-a41-a62$
$a52+a72-a51$	$m+a51-a52-a72$	$6*m-a67-a68-2*a62-a66-a65-a64+a40-a41-a71-a70-a69-a63$	a71	a70	a69	a68	a67	a66	a65	a64	a63	a62	$a41+a62-a40$

● Details

It is an *algebraic cyclic striped* magic square of order 14 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×12 embedded with a magic square of order 10. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are , $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below two examples:

Example 3.29. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 14 based on Result 3 are given by

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	497								
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-69	20	51	497
31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	140	19	52	497
-412	483	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	165	50	21	18	53	497
81	-10	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	-94	49	22	17	54	497
80	-9	30	41	198	1	2	3	4	5	48	23	16	55	497
79	-8	39	32	-127	70	69	68	67	66	47	24	15	56	497
78	-7	38	33	6	7	8	204	-21	9	46	25	14	57	497
77	-6	37	34	65	64	63	-133	92	62	45	26	13	58	497
76	-5	36	35	207	10	-40	11	12	13	44	27	12	59	497
75	-4	35	36	-136	61	111	60	59	58	-45	116	11	60	497
74	-3	34	37	-1	38	39	40	41	42	43	42	10	61	497
73	-2	35	36	72	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	261	-190	497
72	-1	373	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	8	497
73	-2	-302	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	497
497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	574								
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-3	31	51	574
42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	85	30	52	574
-346	428	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	209	61	21	29	53	574
81	1	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	-127	60	22	28	54	574
80	2	74	8	231	1	2	3	4	5	59	23	27	55	574
79	3	39	43	-149	81	80	79	78	77	58	24	26	56	574
78	4	38	44	6	7	8	237	-21	9	57	25	25	57	574
77	5	37	45	76	75	74	-155	103	73	56	26	24	58	574
76	6	36	46	240	10	-40	11	12	13	55	27	23	59	574
75	7	35	47	-158	72	122	71	70	69	-78	160	22	60	574
74	8	34	48	-34	49	50	51	52	53	54	53	21	61	574
73	9	35	47	116	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	206	-124	574
72	10	318	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	19	574
73	9	-236	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	574
574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 213, S_{10 \times 10} := 355, S_{14 \times 14} := 497$ and $m := 71$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 246, S_{10 \times 10} := 410, S_{14 \times 14} := 574$ and $m := 82$.

3.5.2 Flat-Type

Result 4. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 14 in flat way is given by*

a39	a40	a41	a42	a43	a44	a45	a46	a47	a48	a49	$7*a81-a51-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-a41-a40-a39$	a50	a51
a81-a39	a81-a40	a81-a41	a81-a42	a81-a43	a81-a44	a81-a45	a81-a46	a81-a47	a81-a48	a81-a49	$a51+a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+a41+a40+a39-6*a81$	a81-a50	a81-a51
$5*a81-a80-a79-a78-a77-a76-a75-a74-a73-a72$	$a80+a79+a78+a77+a76+a75+a74+a73+a72-4*a81$	a13	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	$5*a81-a13-a14-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21$	a20	a21	a81-a52	a52
a80	a81-a80	a81-a13	a81-a14	a81-a15	a81-a16	a81-a17	a81-a18	a81-a19	$a13+a14+a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20+a21-4*a81$	a81-a20	a81-a21	a81-a53	a53
a79	a81-a79	$3*a81-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34$	$a38+a37+a36+a35+a34-2*a81$	a1	a81-a1	a4	a81-a4	a7	a81-a7	a81-a22	a22	a81-a54	a54
a78	a81-a78	a38	a81-a38	a2	a81-a2	$2*a81-a4-a5-a6$	$a4+a5+a6-a81$	a8	a81-a8	a81-a23	a23	a81-a55	a55
a77	a81-a77	a37	a81-a37	a3	a81-a3	a5	a81-a5	$2*a81-a7-a8-a9$	$a7+a8+a9-a81$	a81-a24	a24	a81-a56	a56
a76	a81-a76	a36	a81-a36	$2*a81-a1-a2-a3$	$a1+a2+a3-a81$	a6	a81-a6	a9	a81-a9	a81-a25	a25	a81-a57	a57
a75	a81-a75	a35	a81-a35	$a81-a7+a8-a5+a6-a10$	a81-a10	a81-a11	$a7-a8+2*a10+a11+2*a12-a1+a2-2*a81$	a81-a12	$a81+a1-a2+a5-a6-a12$	a81-a26	a26	a81-a58	a58
a74	a81-a74	a34	a81-a34	$a7-a8+a5-a6+a10$	a10	a11	$3*a81-a7+a8-2*a10-a11-2*a12+a1-a2$	a12	$a2-a5+a6+a12-a1$	$a22+a23+a24+a25+a26-2*a81$	$3*a81-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26$	a81-a59	a59
a73	a81-a73	$a81+a21-a20-a33$	a81-a33	$a20+2*a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+a28+2*a27-a13+a14-4*a81-a21$	a81-a32	a81-a31	a81-a30	a81-a29	a81-a28	a81-a27	$a81+a13-a14-a27$	a81-a60	a60
a72	a81-a72	$a20+a33-a21$	a33	$5*a81+a21-a20-2*a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-a28-2*a27+a13-a14$	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	a27	$a14+a27-a13$	$a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59+a60-4*a81$	$5*a81-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59-a60$
$a81+a51-a50-a71$	a81-a71	$a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70+2*a71+2*a61-a51+a50+a40-a39-6*a81$	a81-a70	a81-a69	a81-a68	a81-a67	a81-a66	a81-a65	a81-a64	a81-a63	a81-a62	a81-a61	$a81+a39-a40-a61$
$a50+a71-a51$	a71	$7*a81-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70-2*a71-2*a61+a51-a50-a40+a39$	a70	a69	a68	a67	a66	a65	a64	a63	a62	a61	$a40+a61-a39$

● Details

It is an *algebraic flat striped* magic square of order 14 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×14 and two magic rectangles of order 2×10 embedded with a magic square of order 10. It is again composed two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 and two magic rectangles of order 2×6 embedded with a magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and one magic rectangle of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are , $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below two examples:

Example 3.30. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 14 based on Result 4 are given by

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	567								
39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	-18	50	51	567
42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	99	31	30	567
-279	360	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	252	20	21	29	52	567
80	1	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	-171	61	60	28	53	567
79	2	63	18	1	80	4	77	7	74	59	22	27	54	567
78	3	38	43	2	79	147	-66	8	73	58	23	26	55	567
77	4	37	44	3	78	5	76	138	-57	57	24	25	56	567
76	5	36	45	156	-75	6	75	9	72	56	25	24	57	567
75	6	35	46	73	71	70	-107	69	67	55	26	23	58	567
74	7	34	47	8	10	11	188	12	14	-42	123	22	59	567
73	8	49	48	-54	49	50	51	52	53	54	53	21	60	567
72	9	32	33	135	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	180	-99	567
11	10	372	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	19	567
70	71	-291	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	567
567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	616								
39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	31	50	51	616
49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	57	38	37	616
-244	332	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	287	20	21	36	52	616
80	8	75	74	73	72	71	70	69	-199	68	67	35	53	616
79	9	84	4	1	87	4	84	7	81	66	22	34	54	616
78	10	38	50	2	86	161	-73	8	80	65	23	33	55	616
77	11	37	51	3	85	5	83	152	-64	64	24	32	56	616
76	12	36	52	170	-82	6	82	9	79	63	25	31	57	616
75	13	35	53	80	78	77	-121	76	74	62	26	30	58	616
74	14	34	54	8	10	11	209	12	14	-56	144	29	59	616
73	15	56	55	-82	56	57	58	59	60	61	60	28	60	616
72	16	32	33	170	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	152	-64	616
18	17	330	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	26	616
70	71	-242	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	616
616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 243, S_{10 \times 10} := 405, S_{14 \times 14} := 567$ and $m := 81$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 248, S_{10 \times 10} := 440, S_{14 \times 14} := 616$ and $m := 88$.

3.5.3 Cornered

Result 5. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 14 is given by*

$a4-2*a2-a3+2*m-a1$	a1	a2	$a2+a3-a4$	a5	m-a5	m-a11	a11	m-a21	a21	m-a35	a35	m-a53	a53
$a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m$	m-a1	m-a2	$a4-a2-a3+m$	a6	m-a6	m-a12	a12	m-a22	a22	m-a36	a36	m-a54	a54
a3	a4	$a1-a4+a2$	$2*m-a3-a1-a2$	a7	m-a7	m-a13	a13	m-a23	a23	m-a37	a37	m-a55	a55
m-a3	m-a4	$m-a1+a4-a2$	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$2*m-a5-a6-a7$	$a5+a6+a7-m$	m-a14	a14	m-a24	a24	m-a38	a38	m-a56	a56
$3*m-a5+a6-a3-2*a1-2*a2+a4-a8$	m-a8	m-a9	$a5-a6+a3+2*a1+2*a2-a4+2*a8+a9+2*a10-4*m$	m-a10	m-a10	m-a15	a15	m-a25	a25	m-a39	a39	m-a57	a57
$a5-a6+a3+2*a1+2*a2-a4+a8-2*m$	a8	a9	$5*m-a5+a6-a3-2*a1-2*a2+a4-2*a8-a9-2*a10$	a10	a10	$a11+a12+a13+a14+a15-2*m$	$3*m-a11-a12-a13-a14-a15$	m-a26	a26	m-a40	a40	m-a58	a58
$a11-a12-2*a7-2*a6+a3+2*a1+2*a2-a4+2*a8+2*a9+2*a10-a16-2*m$	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	$2*a16-a11+a12+2*a20+a19-2*a10-2*a9-2*a8+a4+a3+a18+2*a7+a17+2*a6-2*a2-2*a1$	m-a20	m-a20	m-a27	a27	m-a41	a41	m-a59	a59
$3*m-a11+a12+2*a7+2*a6-a3-2*a1-2*a2+a4-2*a8-2*a9-2*a10+a16$	a16	a17	a18	a19	$m-2*a16+a11-a12-2*a20-a19+2*a10+2*a9+2*a8-a4+a3-a18-2*a7-a17-2*a6+2*a2+2*a1$	a20	a20	$a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26+a27-3*m$	$4*m-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27$	m-a42	a42	m-a60	a60
$m+a21-a22+a13-a14-a18+a17-a28$	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	m-a32	m-a33	$a18-a17-a13+a14+2*a34+a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+2*a28+a22-a21-4*m$	m-a34	m-a34	m-a43	a43	m-a61	a61
$a22-a13+a14+a18-a17+a28-a21$	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	$5*m-a18+a17+a13-a14-2*a34-a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-2*a28-a22+a21$	a34	a34	$a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42+a43-4*m$	$5*m-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42-a43$	m-a62	a62
$2*a7+2*a6-2*a8-2*a10-2*a9+2*a20+2*a19+2*a16+2*a12+2*a15+a35+a18+a17+a13+a14-a3+a4-a30+a29-a36+a23-a24-3*m-a44-2*a2-2*a1$	m-a44	$2*a44+2*a2+2*a1-2*a7-2*a6+2*a8+2*a10+2*a9-2*a20-2*a19-2*a16-2*a12-2*a15-a35-a18-a17-a13-a14+a3-a4+a30-a29-a36+a23-a24-3*m-a44-2*a2-2*a1$	m-a46	m-a45	m-a48	m-a49	m-a50	m-a51	m-a47	m-a52	m-a52	m-a63	a63
$a44+2*a2+2*a1-2*a7-2*a6+2*a8+2*a10+2*a9-2*a20-2*a19-2*a16-2*a12-2*a15-a35-a18-a17-a13-a14+a3-a4+a30-a29+a36-a23+a24+4*m$	a44	$2*a7+2*a6-2*a8-2*a10-2*a9+2*a20+2*a19+2*a16+2*a12+2*a15+a35+a18+a17+a13+a14-a3+a4-a30-a29-a36-a50-a51-2*a52-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49+a23-a24+2*m-2*a44-2*a2-2*a1$	a46	a45	a48	a49	a50	a51	a47	a52	a52	$a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59+a60+a61+a62+a63-5*m$	$6*m-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59-a60-a61-a62-a63$
$a37+a53-a54+a25+a35+a31-a26-a49+a23-a24-a45-2*a46-a47-a48-a50-a51-2*a52+a4-a30+a29+a17+a13+a14-a3+2*a15+a18+2*a19+2*a16+2*a12-2*a9+2*a20+2*a6-2*a8-2*a10+2*a7-2*a44-2*a2-2*a1-a32+3*m-a64-a38-a36$	m-a64	m-a65	m-a66	m-a67	m-a68	m-a69	m-a70	m-a71	m-a72	m-a73	$2*a64+a68+a38+a36-a37+a67-a53+a54-a25+a73+a72+a71-a35+a69+a70-a31+a26+a49-a23+a24+a45+2*a46+a47+a48+a50+a51+2*a52-a4+a30-a29-a17-a13-a14+a3-2*a15-a18-2*a19-2*a16-2*a12+2*a9-2*a20-2*a6+2*a8+2*a10-2*a7+2*a44+2*a2+2*a74+2*a1+a32-8*m+a66+a65$	m-a74	m-a74
$a64+a38+a36-a37-a53+a54-a25-a35-a31+a26+a49-a23+a24+a45+2*a46+a47+a48+a50+a51+2*a52-a4+a30-a29-a17-a13-a14+a3-2*a15-a18-2*a19-2*a16-2*a12+2*a9-2*a20-2*a6+2*a8+2*a10-2*a7+2*a44+2*a2+2*a1+a32-2*m$	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	a70	a71	a72	a73	$a37-a67+a53-a54+a25-a73-a72-a71+a35-a69-a70+a31-a26-a49+a23-a24-a45-2*a46-a47-a48-a50-a51-2*a52+a4-a30+a29+a17+a13+a14-a3+2*a15+a18+2*a19+2*a16+2*a12-2*a9+2*a20+2*a6-2*a8-2*a10+2*a7-2*a44-2*a2-2*a74-2*a1-a32+9*m-a66-a65-2*a64-a68-a38-a36$	a74	a74

● Details

It is an algebraic cornered striped magic square of order 14, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, where m is the width of the strip. See below two examples:

Example 3.31. Below are two examples of algebraic striped magic square of order 14 based on Result 5 are given by

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/												462	14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/												567		
	128	1	2	1	5	61	55	11	45	21	31	35	13	53	462		158	1	2	1	5	76	70	11	60	21	46	35	28	53	567
	-62	65	64	65	6	60	54	12	44	22	30	36	12	54	462		-77	80	79	80	6	75	69	12	59	22	45	36	27	54	567
	3	4	-1	126	7	59	53	13	43	23	29	37	11	55	462		3	4	-1	156	7	74	68	13	58	23	44	37	26	55	567
	63	62	67	-60	114	-48	52	14	42	24	28	38	10	56	462		78	77	82	-75	144	-63	67	14	57	24	43	38	25	56	567
	186	58	57	-215	56	56	51	15	41	25	27	39	9	57	462		231	73	72	-275	71	71	66	15	56	25	42	39	24	57	567
	-120	8	9	281	10	10	-67	133	40	26	26	40	8	58	462		-150	8	9	356	10	10	-97	178	55	26	41	40	23	58	567
	-116	50	49	48	47	94	46	46	39	27	25	41	7	59	462		-146	65	64	63	62	94	61	61	54	27	40	41	22	59	567
	182	16	17	18	19	-28	20	20	-30	96	24	42	6	60	462		227	16	17	18	19	-13	20	20	-75	156	39	42	21	60	567
	35	38	37	36	35	34	33	18	32	32	23	43	5	61	462		50	53	52	51	50	49	48	-42	47	47	38	43	20	61	567
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	48	34	34	87	-21	4	62	462		31	28	29	30	31	32	33	123	34	34	27	54	19	62	567
	-52	22	272	20	21	18	17	16	15	19	14	14	3	63	462		-97	37	257	35	36	33	32	31	30	34	29	29	18	63	567
	118	44	-206	46	45	48	49	50	51	47	52	52	308	-242	462		178	44	-176	46	45	48	49	50	51	47	52	52	233	-152	567
	-254	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	757	-8	-8	462		-209	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	637	7	7	567
	320	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	-691	74	74	462		290	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	-556	74	74	567
	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462		567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) **First Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 132, S_{6 \times 6} := 198, S_{8 \times 8} := 264, S_{10 \times 10} := 330, S_{12 \times 12} := 396, S_{14 \times 14} := 462$ and $m := 53$.
- (ii) **Second Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 162, S_{6 \times 6} := 243, S_{8 \times 8} := 244, S_{10 \times 10} := 405, S_{12 \times 12} := 486, S_{14 \times 14} := 567$ and $m = 81$.

For more details refer Taneja [65, 66].

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] **G. Bogdan**, Numbers Glaxy: Magic Squares, <https://www.number-galaxy.eu/>
 - [2] **Dwane H. Campbell and Keith A. Campbell**, Welcome to Magic Cube Generator, <http://magictesseract.com>.
 - [3] **H. Heinz**, Magic Squares, Magic Stars and Other Patterns, <http://www.magicsquares.net>.
 - [4] **H. White**, Magic Squares, <https://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
 - [5] **H. White**, Block Magic Squares, <https://budshaw.ca/BlockSquares.html>
- **Different Types of Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares**
- [6] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
 - [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Figured Magic Squares of Orders 6, 10, 12, 14 and 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure, **Zenodo**, November 29, 2022, pp. 1-31, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377674>.
 - [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**,
 - [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, 2022, pp. 1-63, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320116>.
 - [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types of Magic Squares: Even Number Orders From 10 to 26, **Zenodo**, March 26, 2022, pp. 1-167, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6386742>.

● **Bimagic Squares**

[11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Construction of Bimagic Squares: Multiples of Orders 8 and 16.

● **Selfie and Palindromic-Type Magic Squares**

[12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Selfie Palindromic Magic Squares, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Art. 98, pp. 1-15.
<https://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a98.pdf>.

[13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Palindromic, Patterned Magic Sums, Composite, and Colored Patterns in Magic Squares. **Zenodo**,
February 2, 2019, pp. 1-99, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555741>.

● **Perfect Square Sums and Pythagorean Triples Magic Squares**

[14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares Generated by Pythagorean Triples: Orders 3 to 47,
May 28, 2021, pp. 1-119, **Zenodo**, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4837454>.

[15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Generating Pythagorean Triples and Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 31, **Zenodo**, May 28, 2021, pp. 1-153,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4837491>.

[16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Sequential Pythagorean Triples and Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 21, 2021, pp.
1-595, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5009204>.

[17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares with Perfect Square Sum of Entries: Orders 3 to 31, **Zenodo**, July 19, pp. 1-181, 2021,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5115214>.

[18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Minimum Perfect Square Sum Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 31,
Zenodo, July 20, 2021, pp. 1-82, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5116408>.

● **Block-Wise, Bordered and Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

[19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43,
Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.

[20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.

- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares with Perfect Square Sum of Entries: Orders 3 to 47. **Zenodo**. August 16, 2021, pp. 1-317, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5205214>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares with Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic and Semi-Magic Squares with Blocks of Magic Rectangles, May 28, 2022, pp. 1-27, **Zenodo**, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590637>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Magic and Block Bordered Magic Squares, June 03, 2022, pp. 1-70, **Zenodo**, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6621071>.

• Multiple Orders Bordered Magic Squares

- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Bordered and Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, August 31, 2021, pp. 1-148, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5347897>.

• Double Digits and Cornered Magic Squares

- [33] Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.
- [34] Inder J. Taneja, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.
- [35] Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.
- [36] Inder J. Taneja, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [37] Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 16, 20, 24 and 28, August 23, 2023, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10172>.
- [38] Inder J. Taneja, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 108, **Zenodo**, January 29, 2025, pp. 1-33, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14759238>.

• Striped Magic Squares

- [39] Inder J. Taneja, Striped Magic Squares of Even Orders 4, 6, 8 and 10, **Zenodo**, November 10, 2023, pp. 1-34, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15228903>.
- [40] Inder J. Taneja, Striped Magic Squares of 12 – Revised, **Zenodo**, September 07, 2024, pp. 1-30, <https://zenodo.org/records/13725031>.
- [41] Inder J. Taneja, 5600+ Striped Magic Squares of Order 16, **Zenodo**, February 05, 2025, pp. 1-52, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14807639>.
- [42] Inder J. Taneja, Striped Magic Squares of 18, **Zenodo**, June 13, 2024, pp. 1-34, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11629567>.
- [43] Inder J. Taneja, 8000+ Striped Magic Squares of 20, **Zenodo**, March 15, 2025, pp. 1-37, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032524>.
- [44] Inder J. Taneja, Striped and Semi-Striped Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares: Orders 7 to 50, **Zenodo**, March 13, 2025, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15021581>.

[45] **Inder J. Taneja**, Striped and Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 6 to 50 – Recreating Numbers and Magic Squares, March 17, 2025, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15048>

• Upside-down, Mirror Looking and Water Reflection Magic and Bimagic Squares

[46] **Inder J. Taneja**, Upside-Down, Mirror Looking and Water Reflection Magic Squares: Orders 14 to 16, **Zenodo**, January 15, 2024, pp. 1-140, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14649519>.

[47] **Inder J. Taneja**, 2-Digits Universal and Upside-Down Palindromic Magic and Bimagic Squares: Orders 3 to 16, **Zenodo**, April 07, 2020, pp. 1-103, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3743362>.

• Different Styles of Magic Squares

[48] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Orders 6, 8, 10 and 12 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319985>.

[49] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 14 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-40, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319787>.

[50] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-63, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320116>.

[51] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 14, 2022, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320131>.

[52] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles, **Zenodo**, November 15, 2022, pp. 1-88, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7320877>.

[53] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Orders 8, 10 and 12 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles and the Formula $(a + b)^2$, **Zenodo**, September 18, 2022, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7090737>. Also see the following links:

[54] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 14 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles and the Formula $(a + b)^2$, **Zenodo**, September 18, 2022, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7090764>.

[55] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 16 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles and the Formula $(a + b)^2$, **Zenodo**, September 18, 2022, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7090770>.

[56] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles and the Formula $(a + b)^2$, **Zenodo**, September 23, 2022, pp. 1-136, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7108694>. Also see the following links: Different Styles of Magic Squares of Order 18 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles and the Formula $(a + b)^2$.

● Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares

[57] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7, **Zenodo**, September 29, 2025, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17219769>.

[58] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8, **Zenodo**, September 23, 2025, pp. 1-65, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17186001>.

[59] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 9, **Zenodo**, August 27, 2025, pp. 1-92, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16955571>.

[60] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 10, **Zenodo**, September 18, 2025, pp. 1-112, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17149185>.

[61] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 11, **Zenodo**, October 12, 2025, pp. 1-58, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330815>.

[62] **Inder J. Taneja**, Self-Made Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 11, **Zenodo**, October 12, 2025, pp. 1-77, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17330822>.

[63] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic and PanMagic Squares of Order 12, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2025, pp. 1-74, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16370556>.

[64] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 12, **Zenodo**, July 23, 2025, pp. 1-60, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15692014>.

[65] **Inder J. Taneja**, Double-Digit Cyclic-Type Bordered Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 20, **Zenodo**, November 21, 2025, pp. 1-37, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17675032>.

[66] **Inder J. Taneja**, Algebraic Cyclic, Flat and Cornered Striped Magic Squares for Even Orders from 4 to 20, **Zenodo**, December 02, 2025, pp. 1-58, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17793845>.

• Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares

[67] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 14, **Zenodo**, December 03, 2025, pp. 1-68, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17806602>.

[68] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 15, **Zenodo**, December 03, 2025, pp. 1-65, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17806610>.

[69] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 16, **Zenodo**, December 03, 2025, pp. 1-80, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17806619>.

[70] **Inder J. Taneja**, Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 18, **Zenodo**, December 03, 2025, pp. 1-77, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17806626>
